

THE FIRST SILK ROAD CONFERENCE ON FOOD SCIENCE AND FOODOMICS

Conference Dates: November 3-5, 2025

Conference Language: English

Venue: Wyndham Hotel Bukhara

Address: Alisher Navoi 8, Bukhara city,
Uzbekistan

Co-funded by
the European Union

Organized by the project "ECAMPUZ—European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology—ERASMUS-EDU-2022-CBHE," co-funded by the European Union

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***The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics (3-5 Nov, 2025)
Book of Proceedings***

Book of Proceedings

**The First Silk Road Conference
on Food Science and Foodomics**

November 3-5, 2025

Bukhara, Uzbekistan

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Introduction

About the Conference

The *First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics* marks the first international event in Uzbekistan dedicated to bringing together academia and the food industry. The conference is organized within the framework of the EU-funded project "**European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology (ECAMPUZ)**", in collaboration with the **Food Science Society of Uzbekistan**.

The ECAMPUZ project, which concludes in 2025 after three successful years of implementation, has trained more than 70 talented Uzbek students through three intensive training CAMPS covering a wide range of topics in food science and technology. In addition, over 20 young food science PhD students, educators and researchers from Uzbekistan have completed up to three-month academic stays in University of Copenhagen, Denmark or University of Extremadura, Spain.

Conference will host world-leading scientists who will deliver plenary lectures in key areas including food microbiology, food and health, food law and regulation, sensory science, foodomics, oxidation in food and food analytical technologies. The event will also serve as a foundational meeting for future editions of the conference and continued post-project activities of the Food Science Society.

Presentations:

Oral presentations / Flash presentations / Poster presentations

Conference language: English

(Simultaneous English–Uzbek translation will be available for selected sessions.)

Participation in the conference is free of charge.

The organizing committee reserves the right to reject manuscripts that fall outside the scope of the conference. Submissions must be original, with a minimum of 70% originality as assessed by plagiarism detection software. Authors are responsible for the content and accuracy of submitted materials.

Accepted abstracts may be further developed into full research articles for submission to a **Special Issue of an international peer-reviewed journal “FOODS” indexed in Web of Science and Scopus, dedicated to this conference (more information on the next page).**

Special Issue of International, Peer-Reviewed, Open Access Journal “FOODS”

Topic: “STATUS OF FOOD SCIENCE AND NUTRITION IN UZBEKISTAN”

<https://lnkd.in/dgUecpH3>

ECAMPUZ – European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology (ERASMUS-EDU-2022-CBHE) project (<https://ecamp.uz/>), co-funded by the European Union, is pleased to share information about a **Special Issue of Foods (ISSN 2304-8158) "Status of Food Science and Nutrition in Uzbekistan"**

Foods is an international, peer-reviewed, open access journal on food science published semimonthly online by MDPI.

Deadline for full manuscript submissions: 30 April 2026

Information about Special Issue:

Dear Colleagues,

In line with the United Nations’ Zero Hunger Sustainable Development Goals, Uzbekistan has adopted a clear roadmap to strengthen food security and promote sustainable food production as one of its strategic priorities for 2017–2021. This initiative has not only led to the emergence of new food enterprises and the modernization of the country’s food industries, but has also significantly boosted food science education, research, and international collaboration.

In 2022, these efforts culminated in the launch of the first national joint ERASMUS+ Capacity Building project co-funded by the European Union: **European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology (ECAMPUZ)**. The project brought together two European higher education institutions (HEIs) and five HEIs from Uzbekistan. Through ECAMPUZ, more than 20 young food scientists from Uzbekistan spent at least three months in European laboratories, where they advanced their expertise through joint research and exposure to EU teaching practices. In addition, over 70 Uzbek food science students participated in three intensive training camps, where EU faculty introduced them to modern methodologies in diverse areas of food science,

including food chemistry, analytical methods, foodomics, microbiology, data analysis, and more.

As the ERASMUS+ CBHE “ECAMPUZ” project concludes, we are proud to host its final event, “**The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics**”, to be held in the historic city of **Bukhara, Uzbekistan, from November 3–5, 2025**. This Special Issue aims to collect research articles, reviews, and communications presented at the conference and/or developed within the ECAMPUZ project. We also welcome contributions from authors affiliated with other HEIs or associated project partners in Uzbekistan.

This Special Issue is dedicated to showcasing the current state of food science and nutrition research in Uzbekistan.

Participants of “The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics” can get special discounts on Article Processing Charges (APCs) in this Special Issue.

We welcome submissions addressing one or more areas within food science and nutrition.

Focus topics include, but are not limited to, the following:

- ✓ **food processing,**
- ✓ **food raw materials,**
- ✓ **food microbiology,**
- ✓ **sensory science,**
- ✓ **diet–microbiome interactions,**
- ✓ **human nutrition,**
- ✓ **metabolomics, and foodomics.**

More information about Special Issue of FOODS:

https://www.mdpi.com/journal/foods/special_issues/B81YJ76OA6

Sincerely, Dr. Bekzod Khakimov

Dr. Dilbar Dalimova

Guest Editors

Conference Programme

The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics

organized by the “ECAMPUZ – European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology” Project (ERASMUS-EDU-2022-CBHE, co-funded by the European Union) consortium and the Uzbek Society of Food Science and Technology (www.ecamp.uz)

3–5 November 2025, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Venue: Wyndham Hotel Bukhara (Auditorium: Karvon Hall)

Alisher Navoi 8, Bukhara city, Uzbekistan

November 3, 2025 Food Industry Day	
10:00 – 12:30	Registration
13:00 – 15:00	Exhibition by Food Industry including Coffee-break <i>Chairs: Kakhramon Rakhmonov and Akmaljon Boboev</i>
Industry – Academy Bridge <i>Chairs: Khumora Yunuskhodjaeva and Ulugbek Ibragimov</i>	
15:00 – 16:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Questions for Food Industry Enterprises in Uzbekistan:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which of your company’s food products or services are most in demand or best-selling, domestically and/or for export? 2. What are the main challenges or constraints your company is currently facing? 3. Is your company developing any new products or pursuing innovative directions? What resources, technical assistance, or partnerships would you need to achieve these goals? 4. Does your company collaborate with universities or research institutions? If yes, which academic fields or specializations would be most relevant? If no, what are the main factors limiting such collaboration?
16:00 – 16:15	Break
Cluster of presentations by ECAMPUZ trainees <i>Chairs: Kakhramon Rakhmonov and Akmaljon Boboev</i>	
16:15 – 17:45	<p>Sarvar Khodjaev and Samandar Sodikov Food Analytics and Quality Control</p> <p>Ulugbek Ibragimov & Nosirbek Abdurazzakov How can data science help food producers?</p>

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	<p>Zilola Ergashova and Khonsulov Sokhibnazarova Microbial Allies for Future Sustainable Food Production</p> <p>Salijonova Shakhnozakhon Emulsified products</p>
18:00	Free evening

<i>The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics</i>	
<i>November 4, 2025</i>	
08:00 – 08:45	Registration
Opening Ceremony <i>Chair: Bekzod Khakimov</i>	
09:00 – 09:30	<p>Shahlo Turdikulova <i>Vice-president of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Director of the Center for Advanced Technologies, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p>Søren Balling Engelsen <i>Professor, University of Copenhagen, Denmark</i></p> <p>Aziza Abdurakhmanova <i>Coordinator of the National Erasmus+ Office in Uzbekistan</i></p> <p>Sadoqat Siddiqova <i>Rector of Bukhara State Technical University, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p>Bekzod Khakimov <i>Associate Professor, University of Copenhagen, Denmark</i></p>
<i>Chairs: Bekzod Khakimov and Dilbar Dalimova</i>	
09:30 - 10:10	<p>Keynote speaker: Dennis Sandris Nielsen, <i>Professor, University of Copenhagen, Denmark</i> <i>Title: Complex phage communities control gut (im)balances and may hold the key to restore gut biosis</i></p>

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<p align="center">Food Safety <i>Chairs: Bekzod Khakimov and Dilbar Dalimova</i></p>	
10:10 – 10:25	<p>Umidabonu Davlatboeva and Mukhammadsodiq Abduqahkhorov, <i>National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Secretary Expression of Recombinant Antimicrobial Peptides: Mundticin KS and Pediocin PA-1 in Escherichia coli</i></p>
10:25 - 10:40	<p>Flash Presentations (5 min)</p> <p>Jakhongirbek Gulomov <i>Center for Advanced Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Isolation and Purification of Local Strains of Lactobacteria Producing Exopolysaccharides.</i></p> <p>Makhliyo Jumaniyazova <i>Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Evaluation of the Toxicity Properties of Silkworm Pupae Oil</i></p> <p>Ahmidin Wali <i>Xinjiang Technical Institute of Physics and Chemistry, Urumqi, PR China</i> <i>Title: Safety Evaluation of Chickpea Protein Extract in Rodent Models: Acute and Sub-Acute Toxicity Assessment</i></p>
10:40 - 11:20	<p align="center">Coffee-Break and Poster Session</p>
<p align="center"><i>Chairs: Tomasz Pawel Czaja and Zebo Babakhanova</i></p>	
11:20 – 12:00	<p>Keynote speaker: Martin Holle <i>Hamburg University of Applied Sciences, Germany</i> <i>Title: The Road to the EU Food Market – Imports and Novel Foods</i></p>
<p align="center">Green Food Transition <i>Chairs: Tomasz Pawel Czaja and Zebo Babakhanova</i></p>	
12:00– 12:20	<p>Muzaffar Muminov <i>Center for Advanced Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Secretary Expression of Recombinant Brazzein in Escherichia coli Cells</i></p>
12:20– 12:30	<p align="center">Break</p>
12:30 – 13:30	<p align="center">Lunch</p>
<p align="center"><i>Chairs: Mario Estevez Garcia and Zafar Ibragimov</i></p>	

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13:30 – 14:10	<p>Keynote speaker: Sara R. Jaeger <i>Aarhus University, Denmark</i> <i>Title: What is Sensory and Consumer Science?</i></p>
<p>Food Processing <i>Chairs: Mario Estevez Garcia and Zafar Ibragimov</i></p>	
14:10 – 14:25	<p>Shakhnozakhon Salijonova <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Microencapsulation of Algae Oil via Spray Drying for Omega-3 Enriched Cookies</i></p>
14:25 – 14:35	Break
14:35 – 15:00	Flash Presentations (5 min)
	<p>Suliukhan Isaeva <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Quality of Fish Farmed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Modern Methods of its Processing</i></p> <p>Zilola Ergashova <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Study of various possibilities of Lacticaseiobacillus casei encapsulation for food industry</i></p> <p>Marjona Ganiyeva <i>Bukhara State Technical University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Development of Functional Bread Products Enriched with Amaranth and Flax Seeds</i></p> <p>Zarina Karimova <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Development of Gluten-Free Bread Technology with Enhanced Nutritional Value and Gluten Control by ELISA</i></p> <p>Shakhnozakhon Gaipova <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Comparative Study of Mayonnaise from Uzbekistan and Denmark and Its Enrichment with Functional Oils</i></p>
15:00 – 15:40	Coffee Break and Poster Session
<p>Foodomics <i>Chairs: Søren Balling Engelsen and Khumora Yunuskhodjaeva</i></p>	
15:40 – 16:20	<p>Keynote speaker: José Manuel Amigo</p>

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	<p><i>University of the Basque Country, Spain</i> <i>Title: Hyperspectral and Multispectral Imaging together with Artificial Intelligence from Mars to nanoplastics</i></p>
16:20 – 16:35	<p>Sharofiddin Nuriddinov <i>Center for Advanced Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p>
16:35 – 16:50	<p><i>Title: Impact of heat treatment on molecular composition of sunflower, cottonseed, and flaxseed oils</i></p> <p>Umrbek Mavlanov <i>University of Copenhagen, Denmark.</i> <i>Title: A multiplatform spectroscopic insight into fatty acid composition of traditional Uzbek cuisine</i></p>
<p><i>The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics November 5, 2025</i></p>	
<p>Foodomics and Food Processing <i>Chairs: Jorge Ruiz-Carrascal and Sara R. Jaeger</i></p>	
09:00 – 09:40	<p>Keynote speaker: Mario Estevez Garcia <i>Meat and Meat Products Research Institute, University of Extremadura, Cáceres, Spain</i> <i>Title: Ultraprocessed foods as Causes of Non-Communicable Chronic Diseases: Pathophysiological mechanisms</i></p>
09:40 – 10:10	<p>Flash Presentations (5 min)</p> <p>Sardorbek Atajanov <i>Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Determination of vitamins in Melon and its powder using FTIR and UV-Vis equipment</i></p> <p>Nosirbek Abdurazakov <i>Andijan State University, Andijan, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: NIR Spectral Data Analysis for Modelling Wheat Flour Characteristics</i></p> <p>Sevinch Tokhirova <i>Central Asian University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Metabolic Endocrine Disruption by Non-Caloric Sweeteners: Nutritional Controversy or Reality?</i></p> <p>Elmurod Yangiboev <i>National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i> <i>Title: Fatty Acid Composition of Edible Insects as Emerging Protein Sources for the Food Industry in Uzbekistan</i></p> <p>Khandam Karshiboev <i>German-Uzbek dialogue programme on climate resilient agriculture, forage component, Uzbekistan</i></p>

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	<p><i>Title: Development of Rapid On-Farm Analysis Capacity for Climate Resilient Forages with Portable NIRS</i></p> <p>Azimjon Abdunabiev <i>Center for Advanced Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: Gut Microbiome Diversity in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients and Healthy Individuals in the Uzbek Population</i></p>
10:10 – 10:20	Break
10:20 – 10:35	<p>Sodikov Samandar <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: Selection of Encapsulation Technology for Vitamin D3 Fortification of Spreads: Advantages of Encapsulation over Direct Addition</i></p>
10:35- 11:10	Coffee-break and poster session
11:10 – 11:30	<p>Flash Presentations (5 min)</p> <p>Dilnavoz Annaxasanova <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: Optimization of Degumming Technology During Refining of Corn Oil to Improve Its Physicochemical Characteristics</i></p> <p>Maftuna Umurova <i>Bukhara State Technical University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: Assessment of the Suitability for Reuse of Chicken Fat Rendered During Grilling</i></p> <p>Sarvar Khodjaev <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: Ultrasound and Microwave-Assisted Degumming of Soybean Oil: An Efficient Approach for Phospholipid Recovery</i></p> <p>Bobir Kayumov <i>Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</i></p> <p><i>Title: The Effect of Lipolytic Enzymes on Secondary Products in Raw Spirit</i></p>
11:30 – 11:40	Break
11:40 – 12:00	<p>Awards Ceremony <i>Chairs: Søren Balling Engelsen and Dilbar Dalimova</i></p> <p>Best Oral Presentation Best Flash Talk with poster Best Poster Presentation Most Innovative Research Award Most Extraordinary Research Award Best Junior Student Presentations Senior Student Presentations</p>

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12:00 – 12:10	<p>Announcements <i>Chairs: Bekzod Khakimov, Diyora Kurmaeva, Khumora Yunuskhodjaeva</i></p> <p>Special Issue “<i>Status of Food Science and Nutrition in Uzbekistan</i>” in the journal <i>Foods</i> (Impact Factor: 5.0)</p> <p>Establishment of “<i>Uzbek Society of Food Science and Technology</i>” under the Foodomics Laboratory at the Center for Advanced Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan</p>
12:10 – 12:40	<p>Closing Ceremony</p> <p>Prof. Søren Balling Engelsen <i>Overview of the ECAMPUZ project history, achievements and challenges</i></p> <p>Prof. Jorge Ruiz-Carrascal <i>Summary and closing remarks on the conference highlights and announcement of the host and venue for the Second Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics</i></p> <p>Prof. Shahlo Turdikulova, Prof. Dilbar Dalimova and Dr. Zebo Babakhanova <i>Summary and overall reflections on the project</i></p>
13:00	<p>Departure or Free Afternoon/Evening</p>

Keynote speakers

Complex phage communities control gut (im)balances and may hold the key to restore gut biosis

Dennis Sandris Nielsen

*Department of Food Science, University
of Copenhagen, Frederiksberg, Denmark*

dn@food.ku.dk

Gut microbiome (GM) dysbiosis has been found to precede metabolic diseases like obesity, autoimmune diseases like asthma and other gut-related diseases, making intervention through GM manipulation attractive. Bacteriophages (phages) are viruses attacking bacteria in a host specific manner. There is growing understanding that phages (and possibly other components of the gut virome) play key roles in shaping GM composition and consequently influence the trajectory towards health or disease. During recent years the ability of more or less complex consortia of phages and even undefined fecal viromes (sterile-filtered faeces) have shown great promise in alleviating GM dysbiosis related diseases such as *Clostridioides difficile* infection, metabolic syndrome and necrotizing enterocolitis. In this talk, the role of phages in gut health will be outlined and examples of the use of phages and fecal viromes for treating GM dysbiosis related diseases will be given.

About the author:

Danish Academy of Technical Sciences (ATV)

Deputy editor in chief, Gut Microbiology (Elsevier)

Editor, FEMS Microbiological Reviews (Oxford Academic)

Dennis Sandris Nielsen awarded SCIENCE's Dissemination Award-2022 for his willingness and ability to communicate research about the broader societal perspectives of bacteria, viruses and fungi to all kinds of audiences including housewives, schoolchildren, industry and journalists.

The Road to the EU Food Market – Imports and Novel Foods

Martin Holle

*Hamburg University of Applied Sciences,
Germany*

`martin.holle@haw-hamburg.de`

While today a lot of debates in international trade are around the issue of tariffs and bilateral trade “deals”, it is still the technical regulations and standards as stated in the Technical Barriers to Trade Agreement and the rules described in the Agreement on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures of the World Trade Organization that are the major hurdle for market entry in the agri-food sector. Notwithstanding a generally friendly attitude of the European Union to Codex Alimentarius standards, the Union often takes the freedom to deviate from them in order to maintain the high level of health and consumer protection stipulated by the EU Treaties. Compliance with Codex standards is thus insufficient to warrant EU market entry.

Food imports into the European Union must meet the requirements of three different sets of regulations that address human health, animal health and plant health. The strictest rules apply to products of animal origin, which always must originate from an EU-approved establishment in an EU-approved country and composite products that contain ingredients of animal and non-animal origin. For plant-based foods the rules are more liberal, and entry restrictions mainly exist if in specific cases a safety issue was identified, e.g. an increased level of aflatoxins in nuts due to wet harvest conditions.

In addition to the food import regulations, all products entering the EU market are subject to general market surveillance and must comply with all EU food regulations on food safety, hygiene and food information. These EU rules can in some instances be complemented by national legislation. It is therefore important to understand the local situation of the country to which the products are important.

Foods that have not been consumed to a significant extent in the European Union before May 1997 are considered novel foods and are subject to a pre-market authorisation procedure. This applies to products that are created with the use of new processes or technologies (like cell-cultures) as well as traditional foods from countries outside the European Union, that so far have not been present on the EU market. For the group of such traditional foods a simplified procedure exists under the Novel Foods Regulation that allows to consider the history of safe consumption in the country of origin in the authorisation process.

About the author:

Prof. Dr. Martin Holle is member of the German Food Code Commission, the Advisory Board of the German Scientific Association for Food Law (WGfL) and co-editor / co-author of legal guidebooks on Food Labelling, Health Claims and Origin Labelling. He was member of the European Commission’s expert panel for the REFIT (“regulatory fitness”)-check of Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002 and is a regular speaker on all aspects of food law at national and international conferences as well as training events.

What is Sensory & Consumer Science?

Sara R Jaeger

*Department Food Science, Aarhus
University, Denmark*

sara.jaeger@food.au.dk

In this talk, I introduce the scientific area of sensory and consumer science, which traditionally is regarded as a branch of food science and technology. However, it is a dynamic and expanding area of science that is interdisciplinary and draws from theories and methods in social sciences (psychology, marketing, economy) as needed. I present this overview using kiwifruit as a case study (based on published research) and begin by showing how sensory science is used to obtain a detailed understanding of human product perception (e.g., via trained panels and sensory product characterization by consumers). From there, I progress to considering product innovation, focusing on how to measure product acceptance and developing products that consumers like and buy. This leads to consideration of consumers' product perception beyond sensory qualities, and methods used to obtain this information that is vital for market success. Food choice and behavior are also introduced, and provide a bridge to societal impact and the role Sensory and Consumer scientists can have in solving critical global challenges.

About the author:

Sara Jaeger (she/her) is a global leader in the field of sensory and consumer research and has provided a series of highly innovative contributions to the field, mostly in methodology development, where she has pioneered the use of perceptual mapping, conjoint analysis, experimental auctions to measure willingness to pay, the CATA method and the measurement of emotions in relation to the food experience.

Hyperspectral and Multispectral Imaging together with Artificial Intelligence from Mars to nanoplastics

José Manuel Amigo

*IKERBASQUE, Basque Society for the Promotion of Science,
Plaza Euskadi 5, Bilbao 48009, Spain. 2 - Department of
Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country
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Hyperspectral (HSI) and multispectral imaging (MSI) have emerged as essential analytical technologies, providing detailed chemical and spatial information that goes far beyond what traditional imaging can offer. Their combination with artificial intelligence (AI) has transformed how we identify, classify, and understand complex mixtures of materials, enabling quantitative, non-destructive, and spatially resolved analysis across multiple scales.

A defining strength of HSI and MSI lies in their ability to scan entire surfaces, generating vast datasets in which each pixel contains a full spectrum. This capability allows for precise mapping of composition, structure, and changes across objects or scenes, revealing heterogeneity and subtle variations that conventional spot-based techniques might miss. When integrated with AI (a.k.a. CHEMOMETRICS), these imaging systems can handle the intrinsic complexity of HSI and MSI data, mitigating challenges such as high dimensionality, spectral variability, and calibration drift. Different modelling strategies further enhance interpretability and predictive performance, turning raw hyperspectral cubes into actionable chemical information.

During this presentation, real examples from diverse contexts will be shown. We will explore the contributions of HSI and MSI cameras on exploration missions to Martian mineralogy identification, the role of 3D-HSI in studying and conserving cultural heritage objects, and the application of HSI in detecting micro- and nanoplastics in environmental samples. Additional case studies will include the use of MSI and HSI for food quality evaluation and process monitoring in pharmaceutical production, together with forensic sciences, showing how the same core technology adapts to problems as diverse as planetary exploration and sustainable industry. Emphasis will be placed on the importance of model validation to ensure that the results obtained from these imaging systems are robust, reliable, and truly interpretable.

About the author:

José Manuel Amigo received the “2014 Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems Award” for his achievements in the field of Chemometrics and the “2019 Tomas Hirschfeld Award” for his achievements in the field of Near Infrared. He is editor of the book “Hyperspectral Imaging. Volume 32. Elsevier. ISBN: 9780444639776. In Data Handling in Science and Technology.

Ultraprocessed foods as Causes of Non-Communicable Chronic Diseases: Pathophysiological mechanisms

**Mario Estévez^{*}, Alexis Arjona, Julio Carmona, Guadalupe Sánchez-Terrón, Remigio Martínez,
David Morcuende, Carolina Luna, Sonia Ventanas**

Meat and Meat Products Research Institute, University of Extremadura, Cáceres, Spain

* Corresponding author: mariovet@unex.es

Research Institute: University Institute of Meat
and Meat Products Research (IPROCAR)

As the consumption of ultraprocessed foods (UPFs) increases in fully developed and developing countries, the incidence and mortality owing to mortality to cardiometabolic disease such as type 2 diabetes (T2DM) is increasing established as first cause of death among non-communicable diseases in the world. While many epidemiological studies establish this connection, we need to clarify this causal connection by clear and definite pathophysiological connection and mechanisms so that we can unveil the role that specific foods or food components play in the onset of this and other serious diseases. In this paper, we describe the concept of UPF and provide a summary of the most reasonable mechanisms by which the so-called UPFs may be responsible of the connection between UPFs and chronic diseases with particular stress on obesity, T2DM and cardiovascular diseases. We will also talk about certain critical aspects of formulation and processing that may play relevant roles in turning nutritious minimally processed foods into processed foods with negative health outcomes.

About Dr. Mario Estévez:

Dr. Mario Estévez is an internationally recognized expert in oxidation and antioxidation with particular interest in protein oxidation and advanced methodologies to assess both lipid and protein oxidation. He currently serves as member of the Editorial Board of Meat Science (Elsevier) and Associate Editor of the Journal of Food Science and Journal of Food Science and Technology (Mysore).

Oral presentations

OP-1. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

**Secretory Expression of Recombinant Antimicrobial Peptides: Mundtacin KS and
Pediocin PA-1 in *Escherichia coli***

**U.A.Davlatboeva^{1,2}, I.I.Karimov¹, M.A.Abdugakhkhorov^{1,2}, Sh.M.Umarova¹, I.T.Yakubov² and
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Food safety is one of the most pressing global challenges, particularly preventing microbial growth in food remains critical. Chemical preservatives have long been used to extend shelf life, but increasing concerns about their potential health risks have led to greater interest in natural alternatives. Among these, bacteriocins ribosomally synthesized peptides produced by lactic acid bacteria are gaining attention as safe and effective antimicrobial agents.

Mundtacin KS is a class IIa bacteriocin produced by *Enterococcus mundtii*, originally isolated from grass silage. It exhibits strong inhibitory activity against *Listeria monocytogenes*, a major foodborne pathogen, as well as several other Gram-positive bacteria, while Gram-negative organisms are generally resistant. Pediocin PA-1, another well-characterized class IIa bacteriocin produced by *Pediococcus acidilactici*, has also shown significant effectiveness against *Listeria* in various food systems. Together, Mundtacin KS and Pediocin represent valuable natural biopreservatives with strong antimicrobial properties, offering safer alternatives to chemical preservatives. The limited abundance of these proteins in their natural sources necessitates their production through genetic engineering. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to obtain functionally active, secreted recombinant forms of Mundtacin KS and Pediocin PA-1 peptides in *E.coli* cells.

Plasmids constructed to express Mundtacin KS and Pediocin PA-1 peptides along with Maltose-binding protein (MalE) signal peptide in N terminal were generated and were transformed into NEB express *E.coli* strain. Transformants were selected on LB agar plates containing the kanamycin antibiotic. For induction, selected colonies were transferred onto LB agar plates supplemented with IPTG (0.5 mM) and incubated at 37 °C for 24h. The colonies were then inactivated with chloroform vapor. To test antimicrobial activity, an overlay assay was performed: Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA 0,6% agar) seeded with *Listeria monocytogenes* was poured over the Petri dishes containing the inactivated *E. coli* colonies. The plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C, and inhibition zones were observed.

All four selected colonies expressing Mundtacin KS exhibited clear antimicrobial activity against the indicator strain, with inhibition zones ranging from 26 to 30 mm. In contrast, no inhibition zones were observed for colonies expressing Pediocin PA-1. These results suggest that Mundtacin KS can be efficiently secreted in *E.coli* using the MalE signal peptide, whereas achieving successful secretory expression of Pediocin PA-1 remains challenging.

OP-2. SECTION: GREEN FOOD TRANSITION

Optimization of nutrient medium composition and growth conditions to enhance recombinant brazzein secretion in *Escherichia coli*

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Brazzein is a sweet-tasting protein reported to be 2000 times sweeter than sucrose, with stability across a wide range of temperatures and pH values. Its potential as a natural sweetener makes it attractive for food applications, yet limited natural availability necessitates recombinant production and optimization of secretion strategies.

In this study, recombinant brazzein was expressed in *Escherichia coli* NEB Express using the plasmid pSEVA234 and to optimize secretory expression, we evaluated the impact of different inducer concentration, glycine and triton-100X supplementation, and carbon sources. Protein secretion levels were evaluated using dot blot analysis of culture supernatant.

Different IPTG concentrations (0.0, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.5, 5.0 mM) and induction times (0, 2, 4, 6 h) were tested. The highest expression was achieved at 2.5 mM IPTG with 2 h induction. To enhance secretion, we supplemented the medium with glycine (0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0%) and Triton X-100 (0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0%). Both additives independently improved secretion compared to the control, although higher Triton X-100 concentrations showed no further benefit. Notably, combined supplementation produced a synergistic effect, with the optimal secretion observed at 0.5% glycine + 0.5% Triton X-100.

We also examined the effects of different carbon sources (glucose, sucrose, glycerol) at various concentrations (0.5%, 1.0%, 2.0%). While these may have influenced intracellular expression, they did not significantly affect extracellular secretion.

Conclusion: The results indicate that the most favorable conditions for recombinant brazzein secretion in *E. coli* are 2.5 mM IPTG with 2 h induction, supplemented with 0.5% glycine and 0.5% Triton X-100. These findings highlight a practical strategy for improving recombinant protein secretion in bacterial systems.

Effect of Sample Preparation on the Purification Efficiency of Recombinant Brazzein

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Diabetes affects more than 589 million people worldwide, and this number is growing every year. Alongside medical therapy, organizing a safe diet for patients has become an urgent necessity. *Brazzein* is a sweet protein naturally present in the fruit of *Pentadiplandra brazzeana Baillon*, which is considered one of the most promising low-calorie sweeteners due to its similar taste to sucrose. This study aimed to express recombinant *brazzein* in *Escherichia coli* and establish an effective purification protocol.

Two protein extracts were prepared for affinity chromatography. The first was obtained after cell disruption by short sonication cycles. The second was prepared by incubating crude extracts at 75 °C for one hour to denature heat-sensitive proteins before chromatography. Fractions were collected and analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blotting.

Brazzein was detected in both preparations (Figure 1). In the sonicated sample (lane 7), many non-target proteins were present in the flow-through, and the eluate contained *brazzein* together with proteins of higher molecular weight. In the heat-treated sample (lane 9), fewer non-bound proteins were observed, consistent with denaturation of unstable contaminants. The eluate contained a stronger *brazzein* band and an additional protein of ~49 kDa. Protein gel electrophoresis, therefore, confirmed the presence of *brazzein* in both preparations, while small amounts of the target protein were also detected in the non-retained fractions.

Figure 1. Gel electrophoresis of recombinant *Brazzein*. Lane 7: sonicated sample; lane 9: heat-treated sample. Sonication gave higher yields but more impurities, while heat treatment reduced background proteins and improved purity. These results confirm that sample preparation has a direct impact on the quality of purified *brazzein*.

Expression of sweet-tasting recombinant brazzein protein in *Escherichia coli italic* cells in a laboratory bioreactor

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Brazzein is the sweet protein found in the fruits of the Oubli (*Pentadiplandra brazzeana Baillon*) plant, which is native to West Africa. It can tolerate high temperatures, stays stable between pH 2.5 and 8, and is 500–2000 times sweeter than sucrose. The smallest known sweet protein has a molecular weight of 6.5 kDa with only 53–54 amino acids. Because it is protein-based and low in calories, it is harmless for diabetics and a desirable substitute for regular sweeteners that cause obesity. Due to the lack of the natural source, recombinant synthesis provides an appropriate solution.

The aim of this work is to develop a laboratory-scale process for expressing recombinant brazzein in *Escherichia coli italic* using a bioreactor. Mother cultures of *E. coli italic* were prepared, and protein expression was tested under batch and fed-batch fermentation techniques. Different feeding approaches and process parameters were compared to find the most effective conditions. Protein production was assessed by gel electrophoresis, western blotting, and related molecular biology methods.

The study confirmed successful expression of brazzein in *E. coli italic*, with fed-batch fermentation providing higher yields than batch culture. Adjustments to nutrient feeding and process control further improved protein secretion.

In conclusion, this research shows that *E. coli italic* can be used as a host for efficient brazzein production in a laboratory bioreactor. The optimized approach provides a basis for scaling up the process, supporting the use of brazzein as a natural, low-calorie sweetener in the food industry for its application as a natural, low-calorie sweetener in food products.

OP-3. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

**Microencapsulation of Algae Oil via Spray Drying for Omega-3 Enriched Cookies:
Comprehensive Analysis of Oxidative Stability, Microstructure, and Sensory
Quality**

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The incorporation of long-chain omega-3 fatty acids into bakery products is hindered by their high oxidative susceptibility and undesirable sensory impact. Conventional fortification with free algae oil often accelerates lipid peroxidation and deteriorates product quality, limiting consumer acceptance. To address these challenges, this study investigates the microencapsulation of algae oil via spray drying with maltodextrin as a carrier, aiming to improve stability, structural integration, and palatability in omega-3 enriched cookies. Three formulations—control, free algae oil, and microencapsulated algae oil—were systematically compared. Oxidative stability was evaluated through thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS), total fatty acid composition (FA), and conjugated diene (CD) analysis, while microstructural and morphological features were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Complementary assessments included texture analysis (TA), instrumental colorimetry, and sensory evaluation.

Results revealed that microencapsulation substantially suppressed oxidation, with significantly lower TBARS and CD values compared to free algae oil incorporation, thereby extending lipid stability during thermal processing. SEM images demonstrated a homogeneous dispersion of microcapsules within the cookie matrix, maintaining matrix integrity and preventing oil leakage. Textural and color attributes remained within acceptable ranges, and sensory testing confirmed improved consumer acceptability in microencapsulated formulations.

Collectively, these findings establish spray-drying microencapsulation as an effective strategy to overcome the technological limitations of omega-3 fortification in bakery systems. By integrating oxidative, structural, and sensory perspectives, the study provides a robust framework for developing stable, palatable functional cookies that enhance omega-3 delivery in populations with insufficient intake.

OP-4. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Impact of heat treatment on molecular composition of sunflower, cottonseed, and flaxseed oils

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This study presents a multiplatform analysis of sunflower, cottonseed, and flaxseed oils using FTIR, ¹H NMR, and GC–MS to assess compositional changes under heat treatment simulating deep frying. Baseline profiles showed sunflower and cottonseed oils dominated by linoleic and oleic acids, while flaxseed oil was rich in α -linolenic acid. Heating at 180–250 °C increased trans-fatty acids (TFA) from <2% to ~4–6% in sunflower and cottonseed oils and up to ~20% in flaxseed oil. Saturated fatty acids increased by ~10%, MUFA declined sharply in flaxseed oil, and polyunsaturated fatty acids decreased in sunflower and cottonseed oils. GC–MS revealed accumulation of aldehydes and epoxy fatty acids, alongside progressive tocopherol and phytosterol depletion. Multiplatform integration demonstrated that oil type was the dominant factor shaping both baseline composition and thermal stability: sunflower and cottonseed oils degraded gradually with prolonged heating, whereas flaxseed oil underwent rapid, temperature-driven breakdown.

Keywords: vegetable oil, edible oil, trans-fatty acid, trans fat, GC-MS, NMR, FTIR

OP-5. SECTION: FOODOMICS

A multiplatform spectroscopic insight into fatty acid composition of traditional Uzbek cuisine

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High intake of *trans*-fatty acids (TFA) is strongly linked to cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), one of the leading causes of mortality worldwide. While TFAs are largely formed during industrial partial hydrogenation of vegetable oils, they can also occur naturally in household cooking. Gas Chromatography (GC) remains the gold standard for fatty acid analysis, but it is resource-intensive, time-consuming, and less suited for large-scale routine monitoring. There is a growing need for faster, reliable, and environmentally sustainable alternatives. Spectroscopic techniques such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and benchtop Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) offer rapid and green solutions, minimizing sample preparation and solvent use.

In this study, we performed a comprehensive multiplatform analysis of 210 food-derived oil samples from traditional Uzbek dishes, collected across four regions (Khorazm, Bukhoro, Andijon, Tashkent). FTIR enabled prediction of TFA content using the diagnostic 966 cm⁻¹ band, while both benchtop and high-field NMR allowed direct quantification of major fatty acid groups: saturated (SFA), monounsaturated (MUFA), and polyunsaturated (PUFA). Clear differences in fatty acid profiles were observed across food types and sampling regions, reflecting culinary practices and oil usage. Importantly, benchtop NMR showed strong agreement with high-field measurements, highlighting its potential as an accessible alternative for routine food lipid profiling.

This work represents the first systematic multiplatform spectroscopic characterization of fatty acids in Uzbek cuisine, providing novel insights into dietary fat quality and demonstrating the feasibility of FTIR and benchtop NMR as rapid, cost-effective, and sustainable tools for food quality monitoring in regions with limited regulatory oversight.

Key words: *trans-fatty acids, trans fat, FTIR, NMR.*

OP-6. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Selection of Encapsulation Technology for Vitamin D3 Fortification of Spreads: Advantages of Encapsulation over Direct Addition

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Vitamin D3 deficiency remains a significant global nutritional challenge, underscoring the importance of developing fortified food products. Direct incorporation of vitamin D3 into fat-based matrices is constrained by its pronounced sensitivity to oxygen, light, and heat, which leads to rapid degradation and loss of functionality. This study therefore focused on the selection of an encapsulation technology capable of enhancing the stability and bioavailability of vitamin D3 in spreads and bakery products.

Spray drying was employed as the encapsulation method, resulting in two types of microcapsules: a single-layer emulsion with pea protein and a multilayer emulsion with maltodextrin–chitosan. Physicochemical characterization demonstrated that the pea protein system achieved superior performance, with encapsulation efficiency reaching 54.68% and vitamin D3 retention of 2.52 µg/g, compared with 1.41 µg/g for the maltodextrin–chitosan formulation.

To evaluate the functionality of these systems in real food applications, fortified margarines (4 µg/100 g) and muffins (0.95 µg/100 g) were produced, using both direct addition and microencapsulation approaches. This allowed assessment of encapsulation effectiveness in protecting vitamin D3 within fat-based matrices as well as under thermal processing conditions. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirmed the successful incorporation of microcapsules into the product matrices: micrographs revealed that the capsules remained embedded and clearly visible within the muffin structure, even after baking at 175 °C for 18 minutes, demonstrating their protective capacity against processing stress.

The findings confirm that spray-drying microencapsulation, particularly with pea protein as a wall material, offers an efficient strategy for preserving vitamin D3 stability in diverse food systems and provides a technological basis for the development of functional spreads and muffins that may be labeled as a “source of vitamin D”.

Keywords: Sustainable nutrition, Vitamin D3, Microencapsulation, Functional foods, SEM analysis.

***The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics (3-5 Nov, 2025)
Book of Proceedings***

Flash talks (presentations)

***The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics (3-5 Nov, 2025)
Book of Proceedings***

FL-1. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Isolation and purification of local strains of *lactobacteria* producing exopolysaccharides

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The demand for polysaccharides facilitates the use of exopolysaccharides (EPS) in the food industry in increasing amounts. Since many microbially produced EPS are not constrained by the environment, are inexpensive and easy to produce, and possess useful and straightforward anti-climatic properties, they have become crucial for the economy. Lactic acid bacteria's EPS is particularly useful for viscosifying, stabilizing, and improving the texture of foods like cheese, yoghurt, sports drinks, and even candies.

EPS of *Lacticaseibacillus* spp. can reduce cholesterol levels and support immunomodulatory properties, making them therapeutic. In order to create nutritious and healthy foods, it is essential to investigate the EPS from regional strains and their biotechnological qualities. Isolating lactic acid bacteria (LAB) strains from different dairy products and extracting the EPS they generate is the goal of the research.

Materials and Methods: LAB were isolated using MRS medium from plant sources, goat milk, and camel milk. MALDI-TOF (Bruker) was used to identify the strains. Using the ethanol precipitation method, polysaccharides were extracted.

Results: Isolates were isolated from camel milk, three from goat milk, two from pepper, and one from mint. After evaluating the isolates' physical and biological characteristics, it was determined that they belonged to the LAB. There were no antibacterial isolates detected in goat or camel milk. For the next phase, choose antimicrobial strains of *Lacticaseibacillus casei* and *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* that are efficient against food pathogens. Purified 0.3 g/l EPS from *Lacticaseibacillus casei* and 0.075 g/l EPS from *Lactobacillus plantarum*.

Conclusion: It can be claimed that lactic acid bacteria isolated from various sources varied in their exopolysaccharide activity and quantity. The next step will involve examining these polysaccharides' chemical makeup, antimicrobial activity, and safety parameters in order to assess their functional and therapeutic potential for use in food products.

FL-2. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Evaluation of the Toxicity Properties of Silkworm Pupae Oil

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Background: When it comes to silk production, Uzbekistan comes third in the world, with China and India ranking first and second respectively. Today, the sericulture industry of our republic is made up of enterprises producing silk products from more than 30066 thousand tons of mulberry silkworms' cocoons. Currently, this process produces 50% of mulberry silkworm pupae waste. In particular, there are five silk production enterprises in the Khorezm region. These enterprises process 2,500 thousand tons of cocoons per year and produce 28 million silk fibers. As previously stated, this silk industry by-product is either utilized as animal feed and fertilizer, or discarded as waste. This situation primarily results in the waste of raw materials that contain valuable components. It also causes environmental pollution and harms nature when the materials are disposed of as waste. Chemical composition of silkworm pupae 50-60% proteins, 25-35% fats, 5-8% free amino acids, E, B₁ vitamins, calcium, phosphorous, 100g of dried silkworm pupae can provide, 75% daily protein requirement of human individual.

Objective: Study of the process of extracting oil from mulberry silkworm pupae, a waste product of the silk industry.

Methods: 1. Determination of acute toxicity study. The acute toxicity of silkworm cocoon oil was studied on white mice weighing 18-22 g of both sexes in accordance with GST 32644-2014. The test substance is administered in a single dose via a gastric tube. In our case, the dose is administered in small portions over a period not exceeding 24 hours. Before administering the dose, the animals should be kept hungry (for example, in the case of mice, food (but not water) should be withheld overnight. Substances were administered at doses of 5, 50, 300 and 2000 mg/kg body weight. Animals were examined individually after administration of the dose, at least during the first 30 minutes, periodically during the first 24 hours (with particular attention during the first 4 hours) and daily thereafter for a total of 14 days.

Results obtained: the experiments showed that after a single oral administration at doses of 5, 50, 300 and 2000 mg/kg, no visible changes were observed in the behavior and functional state of the animals, and feed and water consumption was normal. All mice were active and showed no signs of intoxication. The mice responded adequately to tactile, pain and sound stimuli. Heart rate and respiratory depth were normal. No mouse deaths were observed within 2 weeks. The LD50 of mulberry silkworm cocoon oil was more than 2000 mg/kg.

Main results: Table 1. Results of acute toxicity analysis of silkworm pupae oil

No	Indicators	According to GST	Results of analysis
1	Acute toxicity	not allowed	More than 2000 mg/kg when taken orally

Conclusion: Tests were conducted to determine the acute toxicity of refined mulberry silkworm oil. The results showed that the LD50 of refined mulberry silkworm oil exceeded 2000 mg/kg, which means that this type of oil was proven to belong to the class of oils that can be used for food after additional tests.

FL-3. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Safety Evaluation of Chickpea Protein Extract in Rodent Models: Acute and Sub-Acute Toxicity Assessment

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Chickpea protein extract (CPE) is a promising ingredient for functional foods, yet its safety profile has not been fully established. This study aimed to evaluate the acute and sub-acute toxicity of CPE in rodent models. In the acute toxicity test, mice received a single oral dose of CPE at 0.15 g mL⁻¹ and were observed for 14 days. No clinical signs of toxicity, abnormal organ morphology, or growth retardation were detected, indicating good tolerance of this dose. For the sub-acute assessment, rats were administered CPE daily by gavage for 30 days. Throughout the study, body weight, food consumption, and general behavior remained comparable to control animals, and histopathological examination revealed no significant organ lesions. The high-dose group displayed altered fecal morphology, which is likely an adaptive physiological response to the legume extract rather than an adverse effect. Comprehensive analysis demonstrates that CPE lacks observable acute or sub-acute toxicity in the tested species and possesses a wide safety margin. These findings provide experimental and theoretical support for the development of CPE as a safe chickpea-based functional food.

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FL-4. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Quality of fish farmed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and modern methods of its processing

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Aquaculture plays an important role in food production and in strengthening the economy of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Due to the arid climate and limited water resources, freshwater fish farming is actively expanding in the region, focusing on species such as carp, common carp, and silver carp. The aim of this study is to evaluate the quality of farmed fish and to highlight modern directions for its processing. The quality assessment methods include organoleptic evaluation (appearance, odor, texture), physicochemical indicators such as pH and TVB-N, and microbiological safety tests. Additional control involves monitoring for parasites, heavy metals, and compliance with HACCP standards.

The fisheries sector of Karakalpakstan benefits from diverse natural and artificial water bodies, including the Amu Darya River, delta lakes, reservoirs, and canals. Between 2021 and 2024, fish farming and aquaculture processing increased from 8.5 to 10.5 thousand tons. This upward trend demonstrates the sector's contribution to food security and socio-economic development.

Processing technologies in the Republic are also evolving rapidly. Traditional methods such as drying, salting, and smoking remain popular, while modern facilities increasingly focus on deep processing and product diversification. Current projects include the establishment of a large canning plant in Muynak, which will significantly expand local processing capacity and introduce new product lines such as smoked fillets, frozen fish using shock-freezing technology, and ready-to-eat items from minced fish (sausages, dumplings, and cutlets). The adoption of waste-free processing principles further improves resource efficiency and sustainability. In conclusion, the fisheries industry of Karakalpakstan demonstrates sustainable growth by combining traditional practices with modern technologies. These developments enhance the quality and variety of fish products, strengthen domestic food supply, and increase the potential for export.

FL-5. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Study of various possibilities of *Lacticaseiobacillus casei* encapsulation for food industry

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The development of stable delivery systems for lactic acid bacteria (LAB) is becoming increasingly important in the functional food and nutraceutical industries. This study investigated the encapsulation of *Lacticaseiobacillus casei* strain LAB 116 using in different microcapsule materials, including sodium caseinate, pea protein, maltodextrin, and multilayer systems incorporating chitosan and acetic acid. The aim was to evaluate the physicochemical properties, encapsulation yield, and viability of LAB over storage.

Encapsulation was performed by emulsification followed by drying, with subsequent analysis of pH, viscosity, water activity, moisture content, color, and solubility. Viability of LAB was determined by plate counting on MRS agar at different dilutions immediately after encapsulation, after 2 weeks, and after 1 month.

The findings revealed significant differences in encapsulation efficiency and bacterial stability across formulations. Caseinate-based microcapsules yielded approximately **49.5 g** of dry powder, exhibited neutral pH (~6.8), and retained moderate LAB viability after 1 month (up to 49 CFU at 10⁻⁷ dilution). Pea protein microcapsules produced less powder (~22.6 g) but preserved higher viability (>300 CFU at 10⁻⁵ dilution) after 1 month. Maltodextrin-based systems showed acidic pH (~3.0–3.5) and relatively high powder yield (~50.2 g), though LAB viability decreased rapidly over storage. Multilayer systems with maltodextrin, chitosan, and acetic acid provided good structural stability, but initial LAB viability was low and declined to negligible levels within 2 weeks. A comparative summary is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of microcapsule properties across formulations

Formulation	Yield (g)	pH	Viability after 1 month
Caseinate + LAB	49.5	6.8	Moderate (10–49 CFU)
Pea protein + LAB	22.6	7.1	High (>300 CFU)
Maltodextrin + LAB	50.2	3.0–3.5	Reduced (≤15 CFU)
Maltodextrin + Chitosan + LAB	43.3	3.5	Very low (≤16 CFU)

In conclusion, protein-based microcapsule materials, particularly pea protein and caseinate, showed the best potential for preserving LAB 116 viability, while carbohydrate-based systems provided higher yields but less stability. These findings highlight the importance of wall material selection for designing functional probiotic microcapsules.

FL-6. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Development of Functional Bread Products Enriched with Amaranth and Flax Seeds

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The rising burden of diet-related diseases, coupled with the increasing challenge of water scarcity in Uzbekistan, underscores the necessity of developing functional foods that ensure energy provision while delivering bioactive compounds with proven health benefits. Amaranth (*Amaranthus* spp.) and flax seeds (*Linum usitatissimum*) are rich in proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, dietary fibers, and antioxidants, and represent valuable resources for bread fortification. This study aimed to develop functional bread using locally grown amaranth and flaxseed varieties from Uzbekistan, improving its nutritional value and therapeutic potential without compromising its technological and sensory quality. Bread samples were produced at the laboratory scale by substituting wheat flour with 10–20% amaranth flour and 5–15% flaxseed paste. Analyses included proximate composition (protein, fat, fiber, and ash), amino acid and fatty acid profiling, antioxidant activity tests, and dough rheology assessments. Sensory evaluation was performed according to standardized protocols, and a comparative analysis with the control wheat bread was conducted. The fortified breads demonstrated significant nutritional improvements, with protein content increasing by up to 16–18%, dietary fiber by 7–10%, and omega-3 fatty acids by > 20%. The antioxidant activity increased 28,7%, contributing to a moderate shelf-life extension. Rheological analysis showed slight gluten weakening, but the optimized formulations containing 15% amaranth and 10% flaxseed maintained a stable dough quality. Sensory tests confirmed high consumer acceptability in terms of taste, texture, and aroma, whereas the estimated glycemic index decreased, suggesting benefits for diabetic and weight-control diets. Incorporating amaranth flour and flaxseed paste into traditional bread formulations enhanced the nutritional and functional qualities while preserving the sensory and technological performance. This approach illustrates a sustainable method for developing health-oriented bakery products tailored to hospital nutrition and preventive diets, with significant potential for broader adoption in functional food markets.

FL-7. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Development of Gluten-Free Bread Technology with Enhanced Nutritional Value and Gluten Control by ELISA

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The aim of this study was to develop gluten-free bread with improved nutritional value and enhanced organoleptic properties. A sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used for the quantitative analysis of trace amounts of gluten in samples, ensuring accurate determination of gluten levels and confirming compliance with international standards for gluten-free products. The primary goal was to create bread with a gluten content not exceeding 20 ppm, verified using ELISA at all stages—from ingredient selection to the final product.

For the study, green buckwheat, quinoa, flaxseed, and psyllium were selected due to their high protein, fiber, and functional component content, contributing to both the structure and nutritional value of the bread. At the initial research stage, the optimal component ratio was established to provide good texture, taste, and a stable gluten content below 20 ppm. After assessing the physicochemical properties, performing ELISA analysis, and conducting sensory evaluations, the best bread formulation was selected for further experiments.

All experimental procedures were carried out under strictly controlled conditions at 22.0 ± 0.1 °C temperature and $51.0 \pm 3\%$ relative humidity, in full compliance with standard laboratory testing requirements. The tests were accredited by TURKAK in accordance with ISO 17025, ensuring the reliability and international recognition of the results. The final formulation fully meets gluten-free product standards and demonstrates improved consumer and nutritional characteristics, confirmed by ELISA results and positive sensory evaluation feedback.

FL-8. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

**Comparative Study of Mayonnaise from Uzbekistan and Denmark and Its
Enrichment with Functional Oils**

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Mayonnaise is an oil-in-water emulsion in which the stability and quality strongly depend on the composition of ingredients and processing methods. As one of the most popular condiments worldwide, it represents not only a product of daily consumption but also a model system for studying the behavior of emulsions in food science. Its texture, flavor, and stability vary across regions due to differences in production techniques and raw materials.

This research was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, 23 commercial mayonnaise samples from Uzbekistan and Denmark were analyzed and compared to identify differences and similarities in their physical and quality characteristics. Advanced methods, including Low-Field Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (LF-NMR), Infrared (IR) and Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, as well as pH and rheological measurements, were applied to assess structural and functional attributes. The results revealed a high degree of similarity in composition and quality parameters between the two countries, indicating that industrial mayonnaise production follows comparable technological approaches despite regional differences.

In the second stage, a standard mayonnaise recipe was enriched with 20% vegetable oils selected for their functional properties. Eighteen different oils rich in bioactive fatty acids were tested to improve the nutritional profile while maintaining desirable sensory characteristics.

These findings provide valuable insights into both cross-country characteristics of mayonnaise production and the potential of functional oils to enhance the quality, nutritional value, and market diversity of mayonnaise products.

FL-9. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Determination of vitamins in Melon and its powder using FTIR and UV-Vis equipment

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In this research, water-soluble vitamins B₆, B₁₂, C and fat-soluble vitamins A and E in melon (*Cucumis melon L.*) products were quantified using FTIR and UV-Vis equipments.

Initially, Calibration standards with specific concentrations of the above mentioned vitamins were imported, they were adjusted to different percentages in the laboratory and the absorbance level was determined. A linear regression graph was constructed for each vitamin.

Preprocessing methods in laboratory: 1) ~10 g of melon pulp was taken; 2) Mechanical homogenization; 3) Water extraction in a rotary evaporator (42 °C); 4) Add 20 mL of distilled water (for C, B₆, B₁₂); 5) Adding 30 mL of hexane (for A, E); 6) Vortex for 5 minutes; 7) Centrifugation (5000 rpm, 10 min); 8) Filtration 0.45 µm; 9) Analyze the extract in a spectrophotometer. Vitamin B₆ gives a peak at 290 nm ultraviolet. B₁₂ at 361 nm. Vitamin A at 325 nm.

Methods used: Analysis of the sample using FTIR and UV equipment. *Mean centering* of the data, *Savitzky-Golay 2nd derivative*, and obtaining a *Linear regression* graph from the control samples. Determination of the concentrations of the prepared melon samples based on the absorbance.

Table 1. Main results:

Objects & Varieties	Vitamins				
	FTIR		UV-Vis		
	C (mg/100 g)	E (µg/ml)	B6 (%)	B12 (%)	A (µg/ml)
<i>Oknovvot</i>	5,95	0,58	2,18965	0,00773	0
<i>Gurvak</i>	5,78	0,59	1,39674	0,01173	0
<i>Oknovvot Powder</i>	0,18	0,58	-	-	-
<i>Gurvak Powder</i>	0,29	0,57	-	-	-

Conclusion: The method used above is considered an economical method because it uses few reagents and gives quick results. It is very important to correctly apply preprocessing methods in the laboratory from cultivated melon varieties and to be able to use reagents cleanly. OriginPro 2021 software was used to perform statistical methods.

FL-10. SECTION: FOODOMICS

NIR Spectral Data Analysis for Modelling Wheat Flour Characteristics

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Wheat flour quality is determined by its physicochemical properties, which directly influence baking performance and consumer acceptance. Traditional laboratory methods for assessing flour characteristics, such as protein and gluten content determination, are time-consuming and labor-intensive. Near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy provides a rapid, non-destructive, and reagent-free alternative for quality control in cereal science.

Studies in the literature have demonstrated the successful application of NIR in predicting protein and moisture levels in cereals. However, comprehensive modeling of multiple flour characteristics remains a challenging task due to the high dimensionality and collinearity of spectral data.

This study investigated the application of advanced preprocessing, dimensionality reduction, and regression modeling techniques to predict multiple wheat flour quality parameters based on NIR spectral data. NIR spectral data of 187 wheat flour samples, measured in the range of 1350–2550 nm at a spectral resolution of 8 nm. Each sample spectrum was averaged over eight replicates to minimize measurement noise were analyzed to model key flour characteristics. Reference measurements included loaf volume, water content, ash content, protein level, gluten index, and wet gluten index. Data analysis was performed using the Matlab based LatentX 2.12 software package. The raw spectral data were preprocessed using mean centering, multiplicative scatter correction (MSC), and Savitzky–Golay derivatization to enhance signal quality and reduce scattering effects. Dimensionality reduction was performed through principal component analysis (PCA), followed by partial least squares regression (PLSR) modeling to predict protein content, water content, loaf volume, and gluten levels. Results indicated that the PLSR models achieved strong predictive accuracy for protein indices ($R^2 > 0.95$), while ash content showed moderate predictability ($R^2 \approx 0.50$).

Figure 1. Linear relationship between PLS model predicted and actual protein in wheat flour.

This work demonstrated the potential of NIR spectroscopy combined with multivariate modeling as a reliable approach for rapid wheat flour quality assessment in milling and baking industries.

FL-11. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Metabolic Endocrine Disruption by Non-Caloric Sweeteners: Nutritional Controversy or Reality?

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Background. The escalating global prevalence of overweight and obesity has contributed to a decline in sucrose-rich product consumption, paralleled by a sharp rise in the use of sugar substitutes. Despite their widespread use, uncertainties persist regarding their long-term effects on metabolic and endocrine regulation.

Objective. This article aims to evaluate the metabolic and endocrine alterations associated with non-caloric sweeteners, with an emphasis on their effects on appetite regulatory hormones and insulin.

Methods. A narrative review of available clinical trials and animal models was conducted, focused on the digestion, absorption, and hormonal responses elicited by non-caloric sweeteners.

Main Results. Across clinical trials, aspartame, sucralose, and acesulfame-K show limited or inconsistent effects on ghrelin, leptin, or insulin regulation, whereas animal studies suggest metabolic disruption. Aspartame alters insulin–glucose balance and poorly suppresses ghrelin, sucralose increases ghrelin, alters leptin signaling and decreases adipokines, while acesulfame-K affects pregnancy, impairs fetal growth and hypothalamic function, demonstrate insulin and leptin elevation and resistance. However, stevia showed improvement of insulin sensitivity, reverse leptin resistance, and reduction in postprandial glucose during diabetes or obesity, both in human and rats, though effects on insulin remain inconsistent.

Conclusion. Non-caloric sweeteners elicit distinct metabolic and hormonal responses compared with caloric sugars. While short-term human studies often demonstrate safety at moderate doses, animal studies raise concerns about potential long-term metabolic consequences. Importantly, long-term, large-scale human trials have not yet been conducted, and most existing studies are limited to short-duration animal experiments. This highlights the urgent need for comprehensive research to better understand the long-term effects of sugar substitutes on human metabolic and endocrine health, particularly in vulnerable populations.

FL-12. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Fatty Acid Composition of Edible Insects as Emerging Protein Sources for the Food Industry in Uzbekistan

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The utilization of edible insects in the food industry has been steadily increasing worldwide, and this trend has recently begun to emerge in Uzbekistan. More than 1,000 insect species have been identified globally as suitable for human consumption. Current research in Uzbekistan focuses on four key species: *Dociopterus maroccanus* (Thunberg, 1815), *Acheta domesticus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Tenebrio molitor* (Linnaeus, 1758), and *Hermetia illucens* (Linnaeus, 1758). To assess their potential application, we investigated the chemical composition and functional nutritional properties of these insects, with particular emphasis on fatty acid profiles. Lipids were extracted using the Folch method, followed by fatty acids via GC-MS. The results showed fat contents of 11.7% in *D. maroccanus*, 17.8% in *A. domesticus*, 21.6% in *T. molitor*, and 7.65% in *H. illucens* (dry matter basis). A total of 14–16 fatty acids were detected across species. *T. molitor* exhibited the highest lipid content, while *H. illucens* demonstrated the greatest fatty acid diversity. Notably, beneficial fatty acids such as oleic acid, linoleic acid, and alpha-linolenic acid were identified in *D. maroccanus*. These findings highlight the nutritional potential of insect-derived lipids for incorporation into the food industry in Uzbekistan.

FL-13. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Development of Rapid On-Farm Analysis Capacity for Climate Resilient Forages with Portable NIRS

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Rationale: Most cows in Uzbekistan could produce much more milk and meat if fed a balanced ration. It is critically important to increase the productivity of local cows through improved rations with higher digestibility and crude protein content. More forages in the crop rotation will also assist in maintaining or even improving soil fertility and structure. The programme promotes the use of more climate resilient forages, improve the production practices, promote analysis and the formulation of balanced rations to increase the productivity of local cattle as a cheaper option than importing poorly adapted high maintenance requirement cattle from the West.

Materials and Methods: hybrid sorghum seeds, biologicals to improve soil biome and plant growth (such as e.g. mycorrhiza and rhizobium), portable NIRS for on-farm analysis and desk-top NIRS for calibration and standardisation, software for cow ration formulation

Results and Discussion: This is 'work in progress'. With livestock contributing 49% to the agricultural GDP yet only having access to 15% of irrigated land for the production of high quality irrigated forage production under constraints of water shortage, climate change and declining soil fertility and structure it is of the utmost importance to measure besides DM yields also the quality. The programme works together with research institutes, central veterinary diagnostic laboratory and dairy farmers to grow hybrid sorghum forage, besides the traditional silage maize, measure the effect of biologicals on soil fertility and growth and do chemical (wet) and rapid NIRS analysis of nutritional value. Milk production in Uzbekistan can be increased and improved when the cattle rations are improved in terms of quantity and quality. More than 90% of dairy cows is kept in rural households and contribute to the quality of the rural families' diet and provide income from sale of dairy products.

FL-14. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Gut Microbiome Diversity in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients and Healthy Individuals in the Uzbek Population

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The prevalence of type 2 diabetes (T2DM) is increasing worldwide and has become a major public health problem. Previous studies have shown that an imbalance in the gut microbiome (dysbiosis) may play an important role in the pathogenesis of T2DM. However, data from Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, remain limited. The aim of the study was to compare gut microbiome diversity between patients with T2DM and healthy individuals in the Uzbek population.

Material and Methods. Stool samples from 38 T2DM patients and 39 healthy controls were analyzed. Bacterial DNA was extracted using the QIAamp PowerFecal Pro Kit. The 16S rRNA gene (V1–V9 regions) was amplified by PCR and sequenced with the Oxford Nanopore MinION (R9.4.1) platform. Reads were processed and taxonomic identification performed using bioinformatic tools.

Results. Alpha diversity analysis (Observed and Shannon indices) showed no significant difference between T2DM and control groups (Observed: $p = 0.49$; Shannon: $p = 0.36$), indicating similar within-sample diversity. This may reflect high individual variability and the limited sample size. These findings are consistent with previous studies. In contrast, beta diversity analysis revealed significant differences. Jaccard ($R^2 = 3.6\%$, $p = 0.001$) and Bray–Curtis ($R^2 = 4.4\%$, $p = 0.001$) indices indicated compositional shifts in the T2DM group, demonstrating disease-associated changes in the gut microbiome.

Conclusion. Beta diversity differences confirmed microbiome alterations linked to T2DM. Beta diversity is an effective measure for detecting intergroup variation and disease-specific shifts. Broader studies, including metabolite profiling, are needed to clarify the clinical significance of these findings.

FL-15. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Optimization of degumming technology during refining of corn oil to improve its physicochemical characteristics

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This study focuses on the development and optimization of a technological process for degumming (classic method) corn oil during refining, aimed at improving its physicochemical and organoleptic characteristics. The degumming stage is critical for removing phospholipids, carrier oils, and other undesirable impurities that affect oil quality. Particular emphasis is placed on the role of temperature during degumming, as maintaining optimal thermal conditions—typically between 50°C and 70°C—is essential for effective hydration of phospholipids, activation of chemical agents, and stabilization of emulsions. Importantly, temperature control during the degumming phase directly influences the alkali dosage required in subsequent neutralization steps. Proper thermal management enhances phospholipid hydration and emulsion stability, which allows for more accurate quantification of free fatty acids and improves the efficiency of alkali neutralization. This contributes to greater overall process effectiveness and improved final product quality. Comprehensive analytical methods were employed, including physicochemical assessments (acid value, phospholipid content, moisture, color, transparency, and peroxidation index), microscopic and spectroscopic analysis of oil composition and structure, and standardized organoleptic evaluations. Statistical tools were used to interpret the data and identify optimal process parameters. The optimized degumming process, incorporating alkali usage and controlled temperature conditions, resulted in significant improvements in corn oil quality: reduced acidity and phospholipid content, enhanced clarity and color, increased oxidative stability, and improved taste and aroma. These enhancements contribute to extended shelf life and greater consumer acceptability. The proposed technology is recommended for industrial application, offering refined corn oil with superior nutritional and technological value for the food industry.

FL-16. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Assessment of the Suitability for Reuse of Chicken Fat Rendered During Grilling

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It is well established that chicken meat is considered a dietary product with high nutritional and sensory value. The content of essential amino acids in chicken meat is significantly higher compared to the meat of other livestock species. In recent years, the number of restaurants and private catering establishments has steadily increased, and alongside this growth, the consumption of chicken prepared in infrared (IR) grilling devices equipped with IR heating elements has also risen.

During grilling under such conditions, a substantial part of the fat melts, drips into the tray, and accumulates in the form of a fatty broth. Despite the practical occurrence of this process, the recovery and use of this fat have not been regulated, and the physicochemical changes that occur in the chicken fat within this broth have not been sufficiently examined. At the same time, the negative impact of lipid oxidation products on human health is widely acknowledged and is considered a key indicator in determining product safety. Since chicken fat contains a higher proportion of unsaturated fatty acids compared to fats of other animals, it may be more susceptible to oxidative degradation during thermal exposure.

To assess the rate of oxidation processes in the fat separated by decantation from the broth formed under real grilling conditions, the peroxide value, acid value, anisidine value, TOTOX index, and smoke point were analyzed. According to standard requirements, the fat sample demonstrated an acid value of 2.0 mg KOH/g, a peroxide value of 6.5 mmol $\frac{1}{2}$ O₂/kg, an anisidine value of 1.85, a TOTOX index of 14.86, and a smoke point of 183°C, confirming its suitability for use in food production.

Additionally, the presence of primary and secondary oxidation products was confirmed through infrared spectral analysis using the IRSpirit spectrophotometer (Zepto Scientific), validating the results obtained through chemical methods.

FL-17. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Ultrasound and Microwave-Assisted Degumming of Soybean Oil: An Efficient Approach for Phospholipid Recovery

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The degumming of soybean oil is of great importance due to the functional and nutritional value of phospholipids in the food and pharmaceutical industries. Conventional degumming methods are time-consuming and do not allow complete separation of phospholipids. This study investigated the effect of ultrasound and microwave irradiation on the degumming process. Ultrasound treatment facilitated water penetration during hydration, while microwave irradiation, through dielectric heating, accelerated separation and reduced processing time.

The results confirmed that both methods, as well as their combination, showed higher efficiency compared to conventional degumming. Ultrasound improved the interaction between water and phospholipids, reducing the fat content of the gums, while microwave treatment enhanced molecular mobility and strengthened water–phospholipid interactions. The combined application of ultrasound and microwave provided the highest phospholipid yield within a shorter degumming time.

FL-18. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

The Effect of Lipolytic Enzymes on Secondary Products in Raw Spirit

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The quality of alcoholic beverages is closely linked to the chemical composition of raw spirit. During the rectification process, the separation of accompanying substances depends on several factors, one of which is the ratio and nature of compounds present in the raw spirit. Lipolytic enzymes, particularly lipases, are known to catalyze the hydrolysis of lipids into free fatty acids and glycerol. These breakdown products play a key role in the formation of aroma-active compounds such as esters, higher alcohols, aldehydes, and organic acids, which are essential for defining the taste and aroma of spirits.

This study aimed to investigate the effect of lipolytic enzymes on modifying the chemical composition of raw spirit and their influence on the rectification process.

The treated samples were analyzed using gas chromatography and liquid chromatography to quantify esters, alcohols, aldehydes, and related compounds. The results demonstrated that treatment of raw spirit with lipolytic enzymes increased the concentration of esters while reducing the levels of higher alcohols and aldehydes. In particular, the addition of lipases promoted the formation of ethyl esters of medium-chain fatty acids, which are associated with fruity and pleasant aromas. At optimal enzyme concentrations, lipases had a favorable effect on the chemical composition of raw spirit, enhancing both taste and aroma. However, excessive enzyme concentrations led to the accumulation of free fatty acids and the formation of compounds responsible for undesirable flavors.

In conclusion, treatment of raw spirit with lipolytic enzymes can beneficially influence its chemical composition and sensory quality. Nonetheless, precise control of enzyme dosage is crucial to maximize positive effects and prevent adverse outcomes.

Posters

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P-1. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Improvement of vegetable oil bleaching technology using acid-activated local bentonite

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Ensuring food safety requires the production of high-quality vegetable oils through effective refining and bleaching. Imported adsorbents currently used in Uzbekistan significantly increase production costs, highlighting the importance of developing cost-effective local alternatives. In this study, Krantau bentonite was chemically activated with hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), and its adsorption and textural properties were comparatively evaluated for use in cotton oil bleaching.

Infrared spectroscopy and X-ray diffraction analyses showed that both acids effectively reduced the calcite mineral content of raw bentonite, which is unfavorable for adsorption. Specifically, 15% HCl treatment decreased CaO from 21.25% to 1.75%, while 15% H₂SO₄ treatment reduced it to 7.36%. SEM and BET analyses revealed that HCl activation produced adsorbents with a higher surface area (101.6 m²/g) compared to H₂SO₄ (64.22 m²/g).

Bleaching experiments demonstrated that 15% HCl-activated bentonite reduced the red color index of sunflower oil from 1.7 to 0.7 units, while H₂SO₄-activated bentonite reduced it to 0.9 units. Similarly, free fatty acid content decreased nearly twofold after bleaching with both adsorbents. Sorption kinetics of chlorophyll and β-carotene indicated that HCl-treated bentonite achieved 95% removal of carotenoids within 40 minutes, whereas H₂SO₄-treated samples reached 90% in 50 minutes.

Overall, both acids provided comparable improvements in bleaching performance, but HCl-activated bentonite exhibited superior adsorption capacity and faster kinetics. Importantly, these locally derived adsorbents can replace imported bleaching clays, lowering costs by up to twofold while maintaining oil quality.

P-2. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Possibilities of purifying vegetable oils using silk fibroin-based sorbents

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In order to make vegetable oils usable, it is necessary to remove harmful substances from them. Cottonseed oil also contains by-products that dissolve in the oil during the process of oil extraction from cottonseed. Some substances are also formed during various technological processes (frying, pressing, extraction, etc.) during oil extraction.

To remove toxic and coloring substances from oils, a sorption process (bleaching) is carried out. Sorbents must have high sorption capacity, low consumption, high bleaching index, low oil capacity, not chemically react with the oil and not leave an unpleasant odor and taste.

Sorbents based on silk fibroin fully meet the above requirements. They do not chemically react with oils and fats. The presence of hydrophilic and hydrophobic parts in silk fibroin, as well as its polyampholyte nature, contributes to the efficient sorption of substances with various properties contained in the oil. At the same time, silk fibroin does not oxidize vegetable oils even when kept for a long time. This means that working with sorbents based on silk fibroin is technologically convenient.

The efficiency of the bleaching process is assessed based on the decolorization ability, the oil capacity of the sorbent, the filtration rate of oil from the sorbent and the acidity of the bleached oil, as well as the peroxide number in its content.

Initially, silk fiber is obtained, fibroin fibers are cleaned from it by the sericin layer, and the washed fiber is hydrolyzed in a hydrochloric acid solution until the fiber becomes powdery. Additional treatment of hydrolyzed silk fibroin with ultra-high-frequency rays increases its sorption surface. On average, 33-35 grams of product can be obtained from 50 grams of cocoon fiber.

The obtained hydrolyzed fibroin samples were used for bleaching cottonseed oil. By bleaching cottonseed oil, the color level was reduced from 17 red units to 8 red units, the acid number from 0.4 to 0.2, the peroxide number from 12 to 2.2, and the moisture content to 0.05. Based on the results obtained, the effectiveness of using hydrolyzed fibroin samples as an import-substituting sorbent in the bleaching process of cottonseed oil was demonstrated.

P-3. SECTION: FOOD SAFETY

Network-Pharmacology and Mechanistic Insights into the Hypoglycemic Activity of Chickpea Protein Extract

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Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is the world's second-most cultivated legume and is widely used to help control diabetic hyperglycemia because of its rich nutritional profile and potential medicinal properties. This study investigated the pharmacodynamic basis and biological mechanisms by which chickpea protein extract (CPE) improves impaired glucose regulation. Constituents of chickpea were retrieved from a traditional-medicine database and screened for hypoglycemic activity using a network-pharmacology approach. Computational analysis identified 205 intersecting protein targets; a protein-protein interaction network highlighted five key targets—matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP9), estrogen receptor- α (ESR1), epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), cyclo-oxygenase-2 (PTGS2), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPARG)—that are likely central to CPE's action. Gene-ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment showed that these targets are involved in inflammatory processes and may protect pancreatic β -cells by modulating the NF- κ B/TNF signaling cascade. The results indicate that CPE exerts multi-target hypoglycemic effects through anti-inflammatory mechanisms and regulation of pathways associated with liver and kidney health, providing a mechanistic foundation for its potential use in diabetes management.

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P-4. SECTION: GREEN FOOD TRANSITION

Low-lactose cottage cheese with whey application

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Background: Lactose intolerance is one of the most common food-related metabolic disorders worldwide, affecting both children and adults. The development of low-lactose dairy products is therefore a priority in food science and technology. Whey, a by-product of milk processing, contains valuable proteins, vitamins, and minerals, but is also rich in lactose and is often underutilized.

Objective: The aim of this work is to explore the feasibility of producing low-lactose cottage cheese through the enzymatic treatment of whey and its incorporation into the product formulation.

Methods: The study proposes to apply β -galactosidase to hydrolyze lactose in whey, followed by the introduction of hydrolyzed whey into cottage cheese at levels ranging from 5% to 20%. The planned analysis will include physicochemical tests (protein content, residual lactose, acidity, moisture) and sensory evaluation (taste, odor, texture).

Main results (expected): It is anticipated that enzymatically treated whey can be successfully incorporated into cottage cheese, leading to a significant reduction in lactose levels while maintaining desirable organoleptic characteristics. The optimal range of whey addition is expected to be 10–15%, which provides enhanced nutritional value, improved texture, and acceptable sensory quality without excessive wateriness or flavor

changes.

Conclusion: The proposed approach offers a promising strategy for creating functional low-lactose dairy products by combining lactose hydrolysis and rational whey utilization. This contributes to expanding the range of dairy foods suitable for lactose-intolerant consumers while improving the sustainability of dairy processing.

P-5. SECTION: GREEN FOOD TRANSITION

Hydrothermal treatment of non -traditional oil raw materials to increase oil yield

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The paper investigates the potential of melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) and watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) seeds as non-traditional raw materials for obtaining functional vegetable oils. Traditional hot pressing methods result in the loss of a significant portion of biologically active compounds, including vitamins and polyunsaturated fatty acids, while cold pressing does not provide sufficient oil yield from low-oil crops. In this regard, an improved double pressing technology with hydrothermal treatment was proposed and experimentally validated. The methodological approach involved a combination of primary pressing (pre-pressing) and final expeller pressing, preceding optimized hydrothermal treatment regimes. In the first stage, the crushed seeds were moistened to 11% and subjected to thermal treatment at 80 °C for 40–50 minutes. In the second stage, the cake obtained after the initial pressing was re-moistened to 12% with steam and treated at 120 °C for 30 minutes under a pressure of 0.5 MPa. The experimental results showed that optimized hydrothermal treatment significantly increases oil yield. Yes, the yield of pre-pressed oil from melon seeds was 26.2%, and from watermelon seeds it was 17.6%, which is 14.5% higher than the control samples. The overall oil yield using the developed technology reached 82–85% of the content in the seeds, whereas with the traditional technology, it did not exceed 36–63%. It is important to note that gentle processing methods contributed to the preservation of essential fatty acids – linolenic and linoleic (omega-3 and omega-6), as well as tocopherols, zinc, selenium, and other biologically active substances. Additionally, improved digestibility of protein compounds and a 20–25% increase in nutrient bioavailability were established. The key feature of the method is the rehydration and short-term heat treatment of the crushed cake, which improves drainage properties and efficient oil extraction without destroying the main biocomponents.

P-6. SECTION: GREEN FOOD TRANSITION

The effect of adding carrageenan on the physicochemical and organoleptic properties of cookies

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Background. Current trends in the food industry are aimed at creating products with improved functional properties and extended shelf life while minimizing the use of synthetic additives. Therefore, special attention is being paid to natural polysaccharides, which can act as stabilizers, thickeners, and texture enhancers. One such substance is carrageenin, a natural hydrocolloid extracted from red algae such as Irish moss (*Chondrus crispus*). The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of adding carrageenan on cookie quality, focusing on changes in their physicochemical properties and organoleptic characteristics. The results will help determine the feasibility of using carrageenan to improve the quality and expand the range of confectionery products.

Objective. Carrageenan is widely used in the food industry due to its ability to form gels and improve the texture of products. However, its use in confectionery, particularly cookies, has not been sufficiently studied. Adding carrageenan to a recipe can affect the physicochemical properties of the dough and the finished product, as well as its organoleptic characteristics-taste, aroma, and texture.

Expected results. The study revealed that adding carrageenan to cookie dough positively impacts its physicochemical and organoleptic properties. The additive increases the product's moisture content and structural stability, reducing porosity and improving texture uniformity without altering flavor or aroma. The optimal carrageenan concentration ensures a soft and flexible texture, enhancing the product's palatability. Furthermore, samples containing carrageenan demonstrate increased resistance to staling and maintain freshness for up to 18 days. These results confirm the potential of using carrageenan to improve the quality and extend the shelf life of cookies.

Conclusion. The study showed that adding carrageenan to cookie recipes has a positive effect on the physicochemical and organoleptic properties, as well as the shelf life of the product. Carrageenan increases moisture content and improves dough structure, resulting in a more uniform and flexible texture of the finished product. Organoleptic properties, including flavor and aroma, remain stable or improve at the optimal additive concentration. Furthermore, the use of carrageenan increases the shelf life of cookies by slowing down staling and loss of freshness. The study results confirm the effectiveness of using carrageenan as a natural stabilizer and texturizer in confectionery production, which can contribute to the development of functional and high-quality cookie-based products.

P-7. SECTION: GREEN FOOD TRANSITION

Medicinal properties and extraction of pectin polysaccharides from the *Alcea Rosea plant*

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Annotation. *Alcea rosea* (hollyhock), hollyhock or pink hollyhock, also known as mallow, belongs to the malvaceae family. The total content of pectin substances in the cell walls of flowers varies greatly from 20 to 35%. Therefore, to study pectin substances, we selected the petals of *Alcea rosea* (hollyhock) as an object. Extracts of rose stock flowers have antibacterial properties. The antiviral properties of hollyhock have been determined. Alcoholic extracts of plant flowers have pronounced antitumor properties. The flowers of the plant have a softening and soothing effect and are used for skin inflammation, rashes and boils.

Methods. Isolation of pectin polysaccharides from the dried petals of hollyhock (*Alcea rosea*). Extraction (150 grams of raw materials) was carried out with a solution of hydrochloric acid and citric acid at a pH of 1.8-3.2, twice. At the first stage, extraction was carried out for 1-2.5 hours at a temperature of 30-90 ° C, hydromodule 1:10, and in the second stage, the process was carried out for 0.5-1 hours at a temperature of 30-70 ° C, hydromodule 1:10, acidic medium pH3.

Main results the yield of pectin polysaccharides from *Alcea rosea* petals at the first stage of extraction (30°C.) is 12.6 and 13.6% when using citric and hydrochloric acids. A further increase in the temperature regime makes it possible to increase the yield of pectin polysaccharides. The greatest optimal yield of pectin polysaccharides from the petals of *Alcea rosea* is observed when using hydrochloric and citric acids at a temperature of 70°C: 19.1 and 19.7%, respectively.

Conclusion. An increase in temperature (75° C - 90° C) leads to a decrease in the yield of pectin polysaccharides from the petals of *Alcea rosea*.

P-8. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Optimized Meal Distribution for University Students Based on a Traditional Uzbek Menu

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Background. Nutrition is a fundamental determinant of health. Contemporary nutrition science emphasizes optimal intake and balanced meal distribution, particularly among adolescents (17–20 years), a period of continued bone, muscle, and neurocognitive development. Transition to higher education frequently disrupts dietary habits, making structured planning essential. A daily energy allocation of 30 % at breakfast, 35 % at lunch, 10 % at snack, and 25 % at dinner supports sustained cognitive and physical performance.

Objective. The study aimed to design and evaluate a culturally appropriate, energy-controlled dietary plan tailored to the needs of students at Central Asian University (aged 17–18). The objective was to optimize daily caloric distribution using a traditional Uzbek menu, ensuring that energy expenditure, physiological growth, and academic performance were adequately supported.

Methods. A structured dietary model was developed based on the average daily energy requirement of 2200–2500 kcal. Energy distribution was calculated across four meals: breakfast (~600 kcal), lunch (~700–850 kcal), snack (~200–250 kcal), and dinner (~500–625 kcal).

Results and Discussion. The proposed plan demonstrated how balanced nutrition could meet both physiological and cognitive demands of students. Breakfasts based on porridges provided slow-digesting carbohydrates, stable glucose release, B-vitamin support for concentration. Lunch, as the largest meal, replenished glycogen stores and maintained productivity, while an afternoon snack stabilized blood sugar and prevented overeating at dinner. Dinner incorporated lean proteins, complex carbohydrates, and vegetables in moderate portions to support overnight recovery without disturbing circadian rhythms. Importantly, the inclusion of culturally familiar foods such as bread, rice, and buckwheat increased adherence while ensuring nutrient density.

Conclusion. The dietary model—tested among 17–18-year-old first-year students of Central Asian University—demonstrates that structured caloric distribution, combined with culturally relevant foods, can optimize adolescent nutrition during a critical developmental stage. By ensuring 2200–2500 kcal/day within four balanced meals, the plan supports academic performance, physiological growth, and long-term health outcomes.

P-9. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Intensification of the cotton miscella refining process

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Introduction. Global production of vegetable oils (palm, soybean, sunflower, cottonseed, rapeseed, etc.) currently exceeds 220 million tons per year, with the main producers being Indonesia, Malaysia, the United States, China, Russia, and Ukraine. Global cottonseed oil production in the 2023/24 oil year is estimated at 5.02 million tons. In the global balance, cottonseed oil production and processing receive special attention because, unlike other types of vegetable oils, it contains higher levels of saturated fatty acids such as palmitic and stearic acids (C_{16:0} + C_{18:0}) and specific components such as gossypol and its derivatives.

Currently, cottonseed oil accounts for more than 50 percent of the vegetable oil consumed by the population of Uzbekistan. There are a number of methods for alkaline refining of cottonseed oil and its miscella, which are aimed at the maximum removal of free fatty acids, dyes and other associated impurities.

The aim of the study was to improve the alkaline refining of cottonseed oil in micelles using non-traditional electrophysical methods.

Research methods. Cottonseed oil in miscella and ultrasonic equipment were used as the study objects. The organoleptic properties of cottonseed oil in miscella (acid value, color, and yield of the finished product) were analyzed based on regulatory documents and standards.

Expected result. It is known that alkaline refining of cottonseed miscella with caustic soda, i.e., NaOH solution, results in significant losses of glyceride and non-fatty components of the oil. Therefore, to reduce losses of valuable oil, it is necessary to break the resulting emulsion using ultrasonic treatment of the miscella and selecting an alkaline reagent concentration that is less likely to saponify triglycerides and associated components. This combined method of cottonseed miscella refining can also be used in processing dark-colored extraction oils containing complex gossyphosphatide-protein compounds. With this in mind, we explored the possibility of combining ultrasonic treatment with cotton miscella during refining. The traditional cotton miscella refining process using a 240 g/l NaOH aqueous solution served as a control. Modern methods for studying the formation of associates from vegetable oil components and the factors that destroy them facilitate the use of electromagnetic forces as a control parameter, which in some cases act as accelerators of the coagulation process and in others as disruptors. Moreover, the organization of such ultrasonic force action is achieved through simple technical solutions.

Conclusion. Thus, intensifying the process of cottonseed oil refining in miscella is undoubtedly considered a pressing scientific and technical challenge. Solving this problem requires the application of knowledge from various scientific fields, including food processing, energy, and others.

P-10. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Fermented Foods and Global Nutrition: Nutritional Promise and Safety Challenges

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Background. Fermented foods, produced from simple raw ingredients, are increasingly valued for their nutritional and cultural roles, forming nearly one-third of the global diet. Unlike highly processed foods rich in sugar or salt, they provide sour and umami tastes, limiting overconsumption. Fermentation also enhances nutrient bioavailability and generates bioactive metabolites that support human health.

Results and Discussion. Probiotic microorganisms and their metabolites, especially short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), deliver multiple health benefits. They reinforce the intestinal barrier, regulate the gut–brain axis, and contribute to immune maturation, with relevance to inflammatory and neurodegenerative diseases. SCFAs alone provide up to 10% of daily caloric needs. Despite these advantages, safety challenges remain. Pathogen contamination—such as *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* spp., and toxin-producing *Staphylococcus aureus*—continues to cause foodborne illnesses. WHO reports that unsafe food leads to 600 million illnesses and 420,000 deaths annually. Chemical hazards further intensify risks: biogenic amines, mycotoxins, heavy metals, and pesticide residues may exert vasoconstrictive, carcinogenic, or immunosuppressive effects. For instance, histamine in fermented fish has been measured at nearly 300 mg/kg, exceeding the EU safety limit of 200 mg/kg, while aflatoxins in maize have been found at concentrations up to 300 times higher than WHO recommendations. These examples are summarized in Table 1, which outlines the levels and regulatory limits of selected hazards in fermented foods.

Conclusion. Fermented foods provide cardiovascular, neurological, and immune benefits but also present risks from pathogens and chemical contaminants. These dangers largely reflect poor hygiene, unsafe packaging, and lack of Good Manufacturing Practices (GMPs). Ensuring their safe integration into modern diets requires harmonized regulations, strict safety standards, and consumer education. Importantly, most studies to date are short-term or animal-based; large-scale human trials remain limited. Future research should focus on long-term safety and health outcomes of fermented foods.

Table 1. Selected examples of biogenic amines and mycotoxins detected in fermented foods, reported outbreak cases, and corresponding regulatory thresholds

Chemical RF	Type of Food	Observed Levels	Acceptable Limit
Histamine (BA)	Fermented fish (yellowtail, South Korea)	293 mg/kg	EU safety limit: 200 mg/kg
Histamine – general	Fish products under GMP/GHP monitoring	Approximately 10% of samples >200 mg/kg	EU safety limit: 200 mg/kg
Histamine – tuna outbreaks	Tuna batches in EU survey	393–5542 mg/kg	EU safety limit: 200 mg/kg
Aflatoxins (mycotoxins)	Pre-harvest maize samples, Democratic Republic of Congo	Up to 300× WHO limit (10 µg/kg)	WHO/FAO recommended: 10 µg/kg total aflatoxin

P-11. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Rapid Determination of Milk Fat Content Using NIR Spectroscopy

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The application of near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy for the determination of fat content in raw milk was investigated as a rapid, non-destructive alternative to conventional chemical analysis. The influence of spectral preprocessing was systematically evaluated for the Partial Least Squares Regression (PLS) based prediction accuracy of milk fat content. Spectra of 26 milk samples were recorded in the 780–2500 nm range using NIR spectroscopy. Preprocessing methods, including mean centering, Multiplicative Scatter Correction (MSC), and Savitzky–Golay second derivatives were applied to evaluate PLSR based models' performance. Sample spectral range and matrix variability were found to be critical factors in fat content determination. After applying optimized preprocessing and outlier removal, the coefficient of determination (R^2) improved to 0.99, while the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) decreased to 0.21%, indicating strong predictive capability. Three PLSR components were sufficient, as the inclusion of additional components did not significantly improve model performance. Overall, the results demonstrate that NIR spectroscopy is a rapid, practical, and accurate technique for milk fat analysis, with promising applications in industrial quality control and on-farm monitoring as an alternative or complement to traditional chemical methods.

Key words: near-infrared spectroscopy, milk fat, PLS regression, spectral preprocessing, quality control

P-12. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Near-infrared spectroscopy coupled with chemometrics (PCA–PLS) for grain protein prediction in cowpea and wheat

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Accurate and rapid assessment of grain protein content is crucial for crop breeding and quality control. Protein content in cereal grains is known to vary widely depending on cultivar, agronomic practices, and environmental conditions. This study employed near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS, 400–2500 nm) combined with principal component analysis (PCA) and partial least squares (PLS) regression to quantify protein content in cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) grains. A total of 12 cowpea samples and 9 wheat samples from the Fergana Valley, each analyzed in triplicate, were used, generating 36 and 27 spectra, respectively. PCA of cowpea spectra showed a dominant first principal component (PC1 = 91.05% of variance) and a secondary component (PC2 = 7.85%), capturing the majority of spectral variation. Wheat PCA revealed PC1 = 64.87% and PC2 = 25.05%, with samples clustering according to distinct growing environments. PLS regression models exhibited high predictive accuracy for protein content in both crops. The cowpea model achieved a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.95 with a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.27, standard error of prediction (SEP) of 0.28, and negligible bias (–0.01). The wheat model yielded an R^2 of 0.94 with RMSE = 0.053, SEP = 0.054, and minimal bias (~0.0009). Overall, NIRS combined with multivariate analysis offers a powerful, non-destructive tool for accurate, high-throughput protein quantification in cowpea and wheat. The developed models are applicable for predicting protein content in grain samples across diverse agro-ecological zones and providing valuable support for food quality evaluation and crop improvement programs.

P-13. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Application of Stationary Ultrasonic Equipment in the Saponification of Cotton Soapstock: Process Optimization and Analysis

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The utilization of ultrasonic technology in the processing of by-products from cottonseed oil refining offers a promising approach to improve efficiency and sustainability in the edible oil industry. This study explores the application of stationary ultrasonic equipment in optimizing the soaping process of cotton soapstock—a secondary product rich in fatty acids and phospholipids. Traditional soaping methods often involve high energy input and longer reaction times, which can be mitigated using ultrasonic assistance. In this work, ultrasonic treatment was applied under controlled conditions with a frequency of 22 kHz and power of 200 W, examining its effects on reaction time, soap formation efficiency, and quality indicators. The process was assessed based on key parameters including soap yield, free fatty acid (FFA) removal rate, and oil recovery. The results demonstrated a notable improvement in process performance: the ultrasonic-assisted soaping reduced the reaction time from 60 minutes (conventional method) to 25 minutes, while increasing the soap yield from 72.4% to 88.1%. Additionally, the removal of FFAs improved significantly, reaching 94.7% compared to 81.5% in the control samples. The oil recovery efficiency also increased by approximately 12%, contributing to better overall resource utilization. Spectrophotometric and titrimetric analyses confirmed the improved physicochemical properties of the soapstock post-treatment, including reduced acidity and enhanced stability. The application of ultrasound also resulted in a more uniform emulsion structure and facilitated the separation of soap and neutral oil fractions. These findings suggest that stationary ultrasonic equipment can serve as a valuable tool in refining by-product streams, offering a more energy-efficient and environmentally conscious alternative to conventional methods. Overall, the integration of ultrasound into the soapstock treatment process not only enhances operational efficiency but also contributes to waste minimization and resource recovery in the vegetable oil industry.

P-14. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Complex processing of oil-bearing flaxseed to produce high-quality oil and functional vegetable-fat paste

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Innovative technology for the complex processing of oil-bearing flaxseeds with producing high-quality, low-yield, “first-cold-pressed” flaxseed oil and cake with a relatively high residual oil content (18-20%) has been developed. This cake is then used to produce functional vegetable-fat products intended for both direct consumption (sesame and nut pastes) and for use in the production of a wide range of food products, such as margarine, bakery, confectionery, and other products.

One of the vegetable-fat systems with excellent taste and beneficial physiological properties, as well as of high demand is sesame paste. The classic formulation for sesame paste (tahini) consists of 100% ground sesame seeds. This paste demonstrates a pronounced deficiency of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) of the ω -3 group, since sesame seeds are not a significant source and contain them only in trace amounts. To ensure the required functionality in terms of the ω 6: ω 3 PUFA ratio, it is necessary to solve the problem of balancing this ratio so that it is equal to 10:1 for preventive purposes and 5:3:1 for therapeutic purposes. Considering this, we propose a method for producing sesame paste by adding a calculated amount of ground flaxseed cake with a residual oil content of 18-20%, characterized by a high content of α -linolenic (ω -3) acid, because flaxseeds are known to hold the record among oilseeds for their ω -3 PUFA content, particularly α -linolenic acid. For a given ratio $y = \omega$ 6: ω 3, the mass fractions of the components, i.e., the ratio of the masses of sesame seeds and ground flaxseed cake, is found by solving the following system of equations for two-component mixtures:

$$\left. \frac{m_1 * c_1^{W_6} * M_1 + m_2 * c_2^{W_6} * M_2}{m_1 * c_1^{W_3} * M_1 + m_2 * c_2^{W_3} * M_2} = y \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$m_1 + m_2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where, m_1 is the mass of sesame seeds, g or kg;

m_2 is the mass of flaxseed cake, g or kg;

$c_1^{W_6}$ is the linoleic acid content of sesame seeds, %;

$c_1^{W_3}$ is the α -linolenic acid content of sesame seeds, %;

$c_2^{W_6}$ is the linoleic acid content of flaxseed cake, %;

$c_2^{W_3}$ is the α -linolenic acid content of flaxseed cake, %;

M_1 is the oil content of sesame seeds, %

M_2 is the oil content of flaxseed cake, %

y is the required ratio of ω -6: ω -3 PUFAs

P-15. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

A study of the influence of plant components on the quality of soft cheese

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Background: Current challenges in soft cheese production include the limited variety of functional dairy products with plant additives, low microbiological stability and short shelf life without preservatives, and the absence of proven methods for adding herbal extracts without affecting texture and flavor. Moreover, there is insufficient research on the impact of basil, ziziphora, and mint extracts on soft cheese quality, complicating product development.

Objective: The research aims to develop a technology for producing soft cheese with the addition of natural herbal extracts to enhance its functional value, improve microbiological stability, enhance organoleptic properties, and extend its shelf life. The study assesses the impact of the added plant components on the product's structural, mechanical, flavor, and aroma characteristics, as well as its overall quality and shelf life.

Methods (in progress and planned): The study utilized both classical and modern methods of physicochemical, microbiological, and organoleptic analysis, as well as laboratory approaches to the preparation and evaluation of soft cheese samples enriched with plant extracts. Fresh or dried abovementioned herb leaves were used to obtain the extracts. Extraction was performed using standardization based on the content of biologically active substances. Samples were prepared with varying dosages of plant components (0.5%, 1%, and 1.5%). The stability of the samples was also studied during storage at +4°C for 14–21 days to identify changes in structure, flavor, and microbiological purity.

Expected results: The study found that the addition of given herbs extracts significantly improved the quality of soft cheese. The physicochemical parameters of the samples containing the additives remained within standard limits, with a slight decrease in pH due to the natural acidity of the plant extracts. Microbiological analysis showed a clear antimicrobial effect of the extracts, reducing total microbial counts and inhibiting mold and yeast growth, particularly at 1–1.5% concentrations. Organoleptic properties, including taste, aroma, texture, and color, significantly improved or remained stable, as confirmed by the results of a tasting evaluation. Furthermore, the shelf life of cheese containing the extracts increased to 18–21 days at 4°C, exceeding the shelf life of the control sample.

Conclusion: The study developed a technology for producing soft cheese with the addition of natural basil, ziziphora, and mint extracts, aimed at improving its functional, microbiological, and organoleptic properties. Experiments confirmed that the addition of plant extracts increases microbiological stability and extends the product's shelf life without compromising its flavor or texture. The results suggest the use of these extracts as natural additives for creating functional dairy products with improved consumer qualities and extended shelf life.

P-16. SECTION: FOODOMICS

Relevance of Molecular Gastronomy in Modern Food Science and Culinary

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The objective was to design food products with minimal ingredients, extended stability, and adaptability for health-conscious diets. The project also aimed to evaluate their potential as a start-up concept in the food sector. Methods involved preparing two sample dishes using spherification. For spherical chicken, minced chicken was blended with broth and pectin or agar, then combined with sodium alginate and calcium chloride to form edible protein spheres. For spherical lemon juice, lemon mixed with calcium lactate was dropped into an alginate bath to create liquid-filled capsules. Both were rinsed and stored under controlled conditions.

The results showed that simple raw materials can be transformed into attractive dishes with preserved taste and nutrition. The chicken spheres offered a protein-rich alternative suitable for healthier diets, while lemon spheres served as refreshing additions to drinks and desserts. Both showed improved shelf stability compared with conventional forms.

Molecular gastronomy provides opportunities for innovation by merging science and culinary creativity. The study demonstrates that novel foods can be developed with minimal inputs, extended storage, and consumer appeal. Such approaches have potential for sustainable production and entrepreneurship in modern food industries.

Table 1. Molecular Dishes Developed

Dish	Technique	Main Benefit
Spherical chicken	Spherification	Protein-rich, healthy
Spherical lemon juice	Reverse spher.	Refreshing, versatile

P-17. SECTION: FOOD PROCESSING

Fermentation and Germination as a Strategy to Enhance the Bioavailability of Iron and Zinc in Wheat-Based Products

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In modern conditions, the problem of iron and zinc deficiency remains one of the most pressing public health issues, especially in countries with a high share of cereal product consumption. One of the key factors limiting the absorption of these trace elements from wheat is the high content of phytic acid, which forms insoluble complexes with metal ions. In this regard, an important research direction is the search for technological solutions that can reduce the level of phytates and increase the bioavailability of iron and zinc in bakery products.

The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of grain germination and sourdough fermentation on the content of antinutritional factors and the bioavailability of trace elements in wheat-based products. The research will compare bread made from standard flour and flour obtained from germinated grain, as well as products prepared with yeast and sourdough. To assess the effectiveness of the selected technological approaches, the content of phytic acid, total levels of iron and zinc, and their in vitro bioavailability will be determined. In addition, the technological and organoleptic characteristics of the bread will be analyzed.

It is expected that the use of germination and sourdough fermentation will significantly reduce the content of phytates and improve the bioavailability of iron and zinc without compromising the quality of the final product. The results obtained may be applied in the development of functional cereal-based products aimed at preventing micronutrient deficiencies and improving population nutrition.

About ECAMPUZ Project: project-driven frameworks as catalysts for advancing food science research and innovation in Uzbekistan.

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<i>Project Title</i>	European World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology
<i>Acronym</i>	ECAMPUZ
<i>Project number</i>	101083216
<i>Program</i>	Erasmus+ Capacity Building in the field of Higher Education
<i>Duration</i>	1.01.2023-31.12.2025
<i>EU grant</i>	717,355.00 Euro
<i>Partners</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology (TICT), coordinator• University of Copenhagen (UCPH)• University of Extremadura (UEX)• National University of Uzbekistan (NUUZ)• Bukhara State Technical University (BSTU) (formerly BETI Bukhara engineering-technological institute)• Andijan State University (ASU)• Urgench State University (UrSU)• Center for Advanced Technologies (CAT)

The food science sector in Uzbekistan has been undergoing significant transformation in recent years, driven by national priorities aimed at sustainable growth and job creation. However, the development of this sector faces several challenges, particularly in the areas of research, education, and industry integration. Young scientists, who represent the future of food science and technology, encounter barriers such as outdated curricula, limited access to advanced research tools, and inadequate industry connections. This lack of support not only hampers their professional growth but also limits the overall potential for innovation in the sector (Bótas & Huisman, 2013; Tekin & Gencer, 2013; Vossensteyn, Lanzendorf, & Souto-Otero, 2008). Moreover, Uzbekistan's food industry is evolving rapidly, creating an urgent need for skilled professionals who are well-versed in modern analytical techniques, food safety regulations, and new food technologies. Bridging the gap between academic training and industry demands is thus critical to ensuring the sector's sustainable development.

In response to these challenges, the European **World Talent Camp for Uzbekistan Scientists in Food Science and Technology (ECAMPUZ) project** was launched as part of the ERASMUS-EDU-2022-CBHE initiative. The project's primary objective is to enhance food science education in Uzbekistan by equipping young scientists with advanced skills and knowledge through collaboration with leading European institutions.

ECAMPUZ aims to facilitate capacity building by offering tailored training programs, research opportunities, and knowledge transfer mechanisms. By providing young scientists with opportunities to learn from European experts

and engage in real-world industry scenarios, the project seeks to foster a new generation of food science professionals who can contribute to Uzbekistan's food sector's growth and modernization.

The ECAMPUZ ERASMUS-EDU-2022-CBHE project is designed to enhance food science education and foster industry integration among young scientists in Uzbekistan. This capacity-building initiative addresses the need for modernized training, skill enhancement, and professional development through collaborative efforts with European institutions. The project comprises training camps, workshops, EU university exchanges, and industry-linked internships, equipping participants with practical skills and theoretical knowledge in food science. Despite facing challenges such as language barriers, logistical complexities, and varying skill levels among participants, ECAMPUZ successfully bridged academia and industry, aligning research and education with industry needs. The project's outcomes include improved technical skills, updated teaching materials, and expanded professional networks, contributing to sustainable growth in Uzbekistan's food sector. The model of ECAMPUZ demonstrates broader potential for similar initiatives in other sectors and regions, emphasizing the importance of international collaboration and hands-on training in developing skilled professionals for emerging industries.

Figure 1. Educational outcomes of the ECAMPUZ project.

The project's skill enhancement programs include workshops and seminars on food science methodologies and industry-relevant practices. These programs emphasize techniques such as food safety management, chemical analysis of food components, and molecular gastronomy principles. By engaging in these workshops, young scientists have developed skills essential for food safety, quality control, and innovation. The practical aspects of these workshops, which simulate real-world food production and processing environments, have further refined participants' abilities to identify and control foodborne pathogens, understand chemical transformations, and implement food safety management systems. As a result, young scientists are not only better prepared for academic roles but also possess the technical competencies required by the food industry in Uzbekistan, aligning their skills with international standards.

CAMPS FOR STUDENTS AND YOUNG RESEARCHERS.

The ECAMPUZ project offers the Food Science CAMPs series as three distinct CAMPs, each focusing on different aspects of this dynamic field.

***The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics (3-5 Nov, 2025)
Book of Proceedings***

CAMP - 1.

Topic: Academic food science upgrade and primary food production.

Subjects covered: Food chemistry, molecular gastronomy and food analytics.

CAMP-1 Period: 18-30th September 2023.

Figure 2. CAMP-1 participants and project coordinators, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. 17.09.2023.

Participants in CAMP 1 gained a strong foundation in food science during a two-week immersive program in Tashkent and Tashkent Region, Uzbekistan. Through innovative teaching methodologies, practical exercises, and industry visits, students acquired knowledge and practical skills. The CAMP 1 was essential to familiarize students with modern techniques and advanced knowledge covering broad areas within the food science field and it provided comprehensive teaching and training using new innovative methodologies applied in the EU HEIs.

During the first week, 18-24th September 2023, of CAMP 1 in "Youth camp" ("Yoshlar oromgohi") in Chimgan, Tashkent region, the CAMP 1 participants (26 young researchers and students) were divided in groups and were assigned a specific contemporary problem present in the food industry (Fig. 2). Then, each group worked on their problems under the supervision of the EU trainers to prepare a presentation which was fully completed by December 2023 with their own solution to the problem based on the learned knowledge and obtained skills.

At the end of CAMP1 program the ECAMPUZ project team organized a visit to a leading brewery plant in Uzbekistan "UzCarlsberg", where the CAMP 1 participants studied the brand new technological line of producing beer, from the raw material to the ready product. Both the project team and the CAMP 1 participants had a chance to discuss matters related to the technology of beer in Uzbekistan: challenges, innovation, implementation of new products for the local people, etc.

CAMP - 2.

Topic: Food Safety and Food Microbiology

*The First Silk Road Conference on Food Science and Foodomics (3-5 Nov, 2025)
Book of Proceedings*

CAMP 2 Period: 1-16 June, 2024

Duration: two weeks

Hosting organization: University of Extremadura

Venue of CAMP-2: Cáceres, SpainES

CAMP 2 on topic “Food Safety and Food Microbiology” was organized by the staff of the Department of Animal Production and Food Science (University of Extremadura) between June 1st and June 16th, 2024, in Cáceres, Spain. CAMP 2 provided an opportunity for 25 participants from UZB HEIs to explore such imperative subjects of food science as food safety and food microbiology. Participants in CAMP 2 gained a strong foundation in food science through innovative teaching methodologies, practical exercises, and industry visits, students acquired knowledge and practical skills.

Figure 3. CAMP-2 participants. At the labs of University of Extremadura and visit to food industry, Spain.

1-16.06.2024 y.

During CAMP 2 program the host (University of Extremadura) organized visits to slaughtering facilities located in two villages in Andalucía during the weekend of the first week of training, and then in the following week near the geographical area where the CAMP was held. During this visit, CAMP 2 participants became familiar with the technological line for slaughtering lambs, sheep, and goats for halal and kosher consumers. Another highlight for CAMP 2 participants was a visit to cheese factory facilities, also in the geographical area where the CAMP was taking place. There, participants had the chance to see how sheep and goat milk is processed and how cheese from these types of milk is produced. By the end of the visit, CAMP 2 participants tasted the produced cheeses. Both the project team and the CAMP 2 participants had the opportunity to discuss matters related to slaughtering and cheese production technology, including challenges, innovations, exports, and more.

* *ECAMPUZ project partner organisations:*

- **TICT** Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology (Coordinator) (P1)
- **UCPH** Kobenhavns University (Co-coordinator) (P2)
- **UEx** Universidad de Extremadura (P3)
- **NUUz** National University of Uzbekistan (P4)
- **BSTU Bukhara State Technical University** (formerly *BETI Bukhara engineering-technological institute*) (P5)
- **ASU Andijan State University** (P6)
- **UrSU Urgench State University** (P7)
- **CAT** Center for Advanced Technologies (P8)

Figure 4. Distribution of participants of CAMP 1 and CAMP 2.

CAMP - 3.

Topic: Food Analytics and Data Science.

CAMP 3 Period: 3-16 April, 2025.

Hosting organization: Urgench State University named after Abu Rayhon Beruniy.

Venue of CAMP-3: Urgench city, Uzbekistan.

Number of participants: 29 from 5 UZB HEIs.

During the first week of the CAMP 3 training, participants attended lectures on Basic Spectroscopy, Quality Control in Analysis, Spectroscopic Fundamentals, IR Spectroscopy, and other related topics.

Participants were divided into eight groups, each consisting of students from different HEIs in Uzbekistan. In addition to lectures, the training included group exercises focused on identifying unknown IR spectra of food products.

On Sunday, the CAMP 3 participants and the ECAMPUZ project team went on a day tour to the ancient city of Khiva, where they explored the rich history, culture, and local cuisine of the Khorezm region.

Figure 5. Participants of CAMP-3. Urgench city, Uzbekistan. 3-16 April, 2025.

“Train-the-trainer strategy” for young researchers, teachers, and PhD students.

A standout aspect of the ECAMPUZ project is the **three-month EU university exchange program according to the “Train-the-trainer strategy”**, which offers 23 young researchers, teachers, and PhD students the opportunity to train at the University of Copenhagen or at the University of Extremadura (Fig. 3). This exchange program has exposed participants to state-of-the-art research facilities, cutting-edge techniques, and collaborations with European experts. The program helps to enrich participants’ research perspectives and broaden their knowledge of global food science challenges and solutions. This international exposure has been instrumental in enhancing their research capabilities, enabling participants to bring back advanced methodologies and integrate them into local academic and research settings in Uzbekistan. This approach not only elevates participants' research output but also contributes to updating educational content, benefiting both current students and future generations of food scientists. Furthermore, the project has encouraged curriculum development and research collaboration.

Figure 6. Distribution of participants of “Train-the-trainer” program.

Participants have worked closely with European experts to develop new teaching materials, research modules, and research case studies, focusing on real-world industry challenges. This collaborative approach has improved classroom instruction and led to applied research projects that bridge the gap between academia and industry. The inclusion of industry-based case studies in the curriculum has been particularly beneficial, as it enables young scientists to address industry-relevant problems while developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

As a result, participants not only contribute to academic innovation but are also better prepared to meet the demands of Uzbekistan’s evolving food industry. The networking opportunities created by ECAMPUZ, through seminars and open-door workshops, have further amplified educational outcomes. These events have allowed young scientists to interact with industry professionals, facilitating knowledge exchange and potential collaborations. Building a professional network is crucial for young scientists, as it opens doors to future research collaborations, funding opportunities, and career advancements. The follow-up evaluations conducted six months to a year after the training have demonstrated sustained improvements in participants' academic roles, research output, and professional integration, highlighting the long-term impact of the ECAMPUZ project.

The ECAMPUZ project has played a crucial role in bridging the gap between academia and industry in Uzbekistan’s food science sector, focusing on collaborative efforts that enhance real-world application of scientific knowledge. This integration has been driven through a series of initiatives that connect young scientists with industry professionals, creating a foundation for applied research, skill development, and improved industry readiness among participants.

One of the key elements of industry integration under ECAMPUZ has been the implementation of collaborative case studies. These projects have been designed to involve young scientists in **solving practical food science challenges**, working directly with industry partners to develop innovative solutions. This collaboration has allowed participants to apply their theoretical knowledge to real-world problems, fostering a deeper understanding of food safety, quality control, and product innovation. Through these case studies, young scientists have gained hands-on experience in addressing industry-specific issues, enabling them to enhance their critical thinking, analytical abilities, and technical skills.

Internships within food processing companies and Start-app accelerator at CAT.

As a result, participants have not only contributed to academic research but have also developed practical solutions that align with industry needs, supporting the sector's growth and modernization. In addition to collaborative case studies, ECAMPUZ has organized **internships within food processing companies** and quality control laboratories. These internships provided participants with immersive experiences, exposing them to industry practices, production workflows, and safety protocols. By working directly in industry settings, young scientists have gained a clearer understanding of the challenges faced by food producers, as well as the regulatory and safety requirements that govern food production.

This hands-on exposure has been instrumental in preparing participants to meet industry demands and improve their employability. It has also facilitated the transfer of best practices from academia to industry, ensuring that participants are well-versed in modern technologies and production standards.

The project has further supported industry integration through practical training workshops led by EU trainers, emphasizing the use of advanced analytical tools and safety standards. These workshops covered a range of topics, including the latest food safety management systems, chemical analysis techniques, and quality assurance measures. By participating in these workshops, young scientists have not only improved their technical skills but have also become familiar with the state-of-the-art equipment and technologies used in the food industry. This practical training has bridged the gap between theoretical education and industry application, ensuring that participants possess the technical competencies needed to excel in food production and safety roles.

Moreover, ECAMPUZ has organized open-door seminars and networking events that brought together academia, industry stakeholders, and young scientists. These events encouraged direct interactions, knowledge exchange, and discussions on emerging industry trends and challenges. Participants had the opportunity to present their research findings, discuss potential collaborations, and establish professional networks with industry experts. These networking opportunities have been instrumental in fostering future collaborations, paving the way for joint research projects, internships, and potential employment, thereby strengthening the link between educational institutions and the food sector.

In terms of project achievements, ECAMPUZ has made notable progress in training and capacity building. Over **60 young scientists, researchers, and educators** have been trained through intensive camps, workshops, and EU university exchanges, equipping them with advanced skills in food science. These training programs have not only improved participants' competencies in analytical methods, food microbiology, and food chemistry but have also aligned their skills with industry requirements.

Furthermore, the project has led to the development of new teaching materials, including updated curricula, research modules, and practical case studies created in collaboration with European experts. These materials have significantly enhanced classroom instruction, making it more relevant to industry needs and improving academic outcomes for current and future students.

Integration with industry.

The project has also successfully conducted over 10 networking events with participation of food industry representatives from Uzbekistan as well as an Uzbekistan Food Industry Association (UFIA), creating a strong foundation for academia-industry collaboration. As a non-business organization from Uzbekistan with more than 2500 members, the Association plays an important role in ensuring the highest quality standards and sufficient level of food production in accordance with scientifically approved standards. At the same time, UFIA oversees

the creation and maintenance of the basic food stocks needed in adverse conditions, supporting food security and development of the food industry in the region, which supports the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 2). These events have helped establish connections that facilitate knowledge transfer, collaborative research, and professional integration of young scientists into the food sector. By providing platforms for direct interaction with industry stakeholders, these events have increased the likelihood of sustainable collaborations that benefit both academia and industry.

Table 1. The details of industry integration and project achievements for the ECAMPUZ project.

Category	Details	Impact
Industry Integration		
Collaborative Case Studies	Joint projects between young scientists, students focused on real-world food science challenges.	Enabled participants to apply theoretical knowledge to practical issues, fostering problem-solving skills and innovation.
Internships	Internships at food processing companies and quality control labs, visits to food companies in Uzbekistan and Spain, providing hands-on industry experience.	Improved understanding of industry practices, production workflows, and safety protocols, making participants industry-ready.
Practical Training	Workshops conducted in collaboration with industry experts, emphasizing modern technologies and safety standards.	Enhanced participants' technical skills and provided exposure to cutting-edge industry technologies and equipment.
Industry Seminars	Open-door seminars with industry stakeholders, encouraging direct interactions and knowledge exchange.	Expanded participants' professional networks, facilitating future collaborations and industry linkages.
Project Achievements		
Number of Participants Trained	Over 60 young scientists, researchers, and educators trained through camps, workshops, and EU exchanges.	Increased competency in advanced food science topics and industry-relevant skills among participants.
New Teaching Materials Developed	Creation of updated curricula, research modules, and practical case studies in collaboration with EU experts.	Enhanced academic resources, improving classroom teaching and aligning with industry needs.
Networking Events	Successful organization of over 10 networking events, including seminars and workshops with industry experts.	Strengthened academia-industry connections, creating pathways for research collaborations, internships, and employment.

The implementation of the ECAMPUZ project encountered several challenges that required strategic adaptations to ensure its success in enhancing food science education and industry integration in Uzbekistan. One of the primary challenges was the logistical complexity of organizing training camps, workshops, and university exchanges across multiple countries. Coordinating participants' travel, accommodation, and training schedules, especially for the EU exchanges, involved extensive planning and posed administrative hurdles. To address this, the project team established a dedicated coordination unit that worked closely with partner universities to streamline processes, manage participant logistics, and ensure compliance with travel regulations and schedules.

The project also faced issues related to varying levels of technical expertise among participants. While some participants were well-versed in basic food science concepts, others had limited experience with advanced analytical techniques. This disparity was addressed by implementing a tiered training approach, where participants were grouped based on their existing skill levels. Beginners received foundational training before progressing to advanced techniques, while more experienced participants engaged in specialized workshops. This adaptive approach ensured that all participants, regardless of their initial skill levels, gained relevant knowledge and technical skills. The integration of academic training with industry needs also posed challenges, particularly in aligning research projects with real-world applications. Industry partners were initially hesitant to fully engage in collaborative projects, primarily due to differences in research priorities and timelines. The project team addressed this by conducting regular meetings with industry stakeholders to better understand their needs and expectations, adjusting research focus areas to match industry demands. By actively involving industry partners in designing case studies and internships, the project fostered mutual trust and collaboration, ultimately achieving its integration goals.

CAT Accelerator program

Figure 7. Participants and coordinators of Accelerator program at CAT, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. 04.09.2024 y.

The opening ceremony of the C.A.T. Science Accelerator program was held at the Center for Advanced Technologies on September 4, 2024. Vice President of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shahlo Turdiqulova welcomed the program participants and emphasized the importance of startups in implementing innovative ideas in Uzbekistan. Shahlo Turdiqulova also spoke about the successful programs of the C.A.T. Science Accelerator since its establishment in 2018.

Deputy Director of the Center for Advanced Technologies Dilbar Dalimova welcomed the guests of the ceremony and noted that the C.A.T. Science Accelerator participants were selected from hundreds of applicants from across Uzbekistan.

The participants had the opportunity to meet their mentors in person. The mentors provided detailed information about the main aspects of the program, the development and improvement of projects by the teams during the period leading up to Demo Day, as well as the event itself.

Participants were introduced to the rules of the accelerator. An interactive session was also held, during which the teams had the opportunity to briefly present their projects and get to know each other. The success of the ECAMPUZ project in Uzbekistan demonstrates the potential for similar capacity-building initiatives to significantly enhance education and industry integration in other regions, particularly in developing countries. By focusing on a combination of training, skill development, and practical industry engagement, ECAMPUZ has created a sustainable model that can be adapted to other educational sectors, such as healthcare, agriculture, or environmental science. The project's tiered training approach, which effectively addresses varying skill levels among participants, is a scalable model that can be replicated in diverse contexts, ensuring inclusivity and comprehensive skill development.

The project's emphasis on international collaboration and knowledge exchange also holds broader implications for global education. By facilitating university exchanges and collaborative research, similar projects can enhance the technical skills and global perspectives of participants, contributing to a more interconnected and innovative academic community. The model of integrating industry needs into academic training can be particularly beneficial for regions seeking to develop industries aligned with global standards, as it ensures that graduates are well-prepared to contribute to economic growth and sectoral modernization. Furthermore, the focus on networking and professional development seen in ECAMPUZ can serve as a blueprint for strengthening academia-industry relations in other sectors. Regular networking events, seminars, and collaborative projects encourage ongoing dialogue between educational institutions and industries, paving the way for continuous knowledge transfer and innovation. This approach not only enhances participants' professional networks but also supports long-term sectoral growth by aligning academic outcomes with industry requirements.

Conclusion

The ECAMPUZ project helped to strengthen food science education and facilitated industry integration for young scientists in Uzbekistan. By implementing a comprehensive training model that includes hands-on workshops, EU university exchanges, and collaborative research projects, ECAMPUZ has addressed the gaps in education and professional development within the food sector. The project's adaptive strategies ensured effective participation and skill improvement, overcoming challenges related to language, logistics, and diverse expertise levels. As a result, participants have gained advanced competencies from EU teachers, enabling them to contribute to both academia and industry. The project not only supports sustainable growth in Uzbekistan's food sector but also serves as a replicable model for other regions and sectors, demonstrating the value of international collaboration, practical training, and industry-aligned education. The outcomes of ECAMPUZ underscore the importance of aligning academic programs with industry demands to create a skilled, job-ready workforce capable of driving innovation and development.

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**BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH CONFERENCE
“THE FIRST SILK ROAD CONFERENCE
ON FOOD SCIENCE AND FOODOMICS”, 100 p.
3-5 November, 2025, Bukhara city, Uzbekistan**

Responsible secretary: Khumora Yunuskhodjaeva, Zebo Babakhanova

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- Food Safety
- Food Processing
- Green Food Transition

KEY HIGHLIGHTS

NOVEMBER 3

Academia meets industry: Uniting Uzbekistan's Food Industry and Academia in Bukhara

NOVEMBER 4

4 International Keynote Speakers, 5 oral presentations, 8 flash presentations, 17 posters

NOVEMBER 5

1 International Keynote speaker, 1 oral presentation, 10 flash presentations, 18 posters

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